

SPN04 - WORD FINAL <nt>
(DIE AUSLAUTVERHÄRTUNG)

This paper revises the author's original (1989¹, 1996²) analysis of Notker's fortitions. The revision merges Notker's syllable initial fortition, the Anlautgesetz, with his syllable final fortition, the Auslautverhärtung.³ To do this, the analysis builds on patterns first detailed by Moulton⁴ and Page.⁵ The essay falls into five parts:

- 1) A brief introduction into Notker and his Old High German Anlautgesetz, followed by a similarly brief introduction into the Middle High German Auslautverhärtung.
- 2) The standard theory - after vowels and liquids, Notker maintains a lenis≠fortis contrast syllable finally, or at least in the dental stops. In addition, an emerging Auslautverhärtung may occasionally reduce this contrast to just fortis. After nasals however, the lenis≠fortis contrast always collapses to just fortis, or again at least in the dental stops.
- 3) A summary of how all obstruents contrast in Notker. The detail is in Appendix A.

¹ Nederloe, Christian (1989). *SPN00 - The de Nuptiis System*. pp. 66-74. SPN is short for "Spelling Patterns of Notker", and links together a series of papers, some already posted and some still in draft. SPN01 is the main theoretical work, and lays out a method for reconstructing the spoken and written systems of medieval texts. SPN00 serves as notes for that - a work drafted, but never handed in, for an undergraduate course. The papers following SPN01 (so SPN02, SPN03, SPN04 and upcoming ones in draft) are written in the more approachable style of a journal article, and usually focus on a single spelling pattern. Each of these is titled by a spelling pattern and subtitled by its process. So, for example, SPN02 is titled "Word Initial <s> and <h>" and subtitled "Das Anlautgesetz".

² Nederloe, Christian (1996). *SPN01 - The Spelling Patterns of Notker*. pp. 72-79.

³ Syllable medial fortition, a trivial process in Notker, is also merged in.

⁴ Moulton, William (1979). "Notker's Anlautgesetz". *Linguistic Method: Essays in Honor of Herbert Penzl*. The Hague: Mouton. pp. 241-251.

⁵ Page, Richard (2013). "Notker's Anlautgesetz and the Neutralization of Contrasts". *Beiträge zur Geschichte der deutschen Sprache und Literatur*. vol. 135, pp. 515-534.

- 4) An investigation into Notker's Auslautverhärtung, to see if that fortition is sensitive to sonority gradations, similar to Notker's Anlautgesetz. The analysis includes spelling rules from previous papers, but also a newly proposed one for word final <nt>. The detail is in Appendix B.
- 5) The merger of Notker's Anlautgesetz and Auslautverhärtung into a single speech rule, Notker's Verhärtung.

1) Notker's Anlautgesetz and the Auslautverhärtung

Notker Teutonicus lived from 950 to 1022, much of his life in the Swiss monastery of Saint Gall. He translated several Latin manuscripts into his native Old Alemannic, a dialect of Old High German. His works are famous for an alternation in obstruents that has fascinated scholars since the Brothers Grimm.⁶ Initial <b,d,g,u> are written <p,t,k,f>, unless preceded by a sonorant (<l,m,n,r> or any vowel graph). An example would be the <g≠k> alternation in *gegân* and *nahkân*, so after two different prefixes before the word for 'to go'.⁷ Articles written in both German and English refer to the pattern as Notker's Anlautgesetz,⁸ a term translated by N.E. Collinge as "law of initials".⁹

⁶ Grimm, Jacob (1822). *Deutsche Grammatik*. Göttingen: Dietrich. p. 107.

⁷ For more examples, see Nederloe, Christian (1997). *SPN02 - Word Initial <s> and <h>*, *Das Anlautgesetz*. pp. 2-3.

⁸ For a review of Anlautgesetz scholarship until 1955, see: Penzl, Herbert (1955). "Zur Erklärung von Notkers Anlautgesetz". *Zeitschrift für deutsches Altertum und deutsche Literatur*. vol. 86. pp. 196-210.

For a review of more recent work, see:

Luxner, Bernhard (2013). *Notkers Anlautgesetz im Kontext der diachronen Sprachwissenschaft und modernen Dialektologie*. Jena: Meisterarbeit.

For a broader overview of Notker, both his teaching methods and his spelling patterns, there is no more thoroughly researched or beautifully written book than: Grotans, Anna (2006). *Reading in Medieval St. Gall*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

⁹ Collinge, N.E. (1985). *The Laws of Indo-European*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. p. 121.

Dozens of scribes and poets wrote down their Middle High German dialects from 1050 to 1350. In at least our normalized texts, they mark a fortition syllable finally. An example would be the <g#c> alternation in *dër tac*, and *die tage*, the nominative singular and plural for 'day', which of course reflect the process spoken (but not marked) in Modern German *der Tag* and *die Tage*.¹⁰ Articles written in both German and English refer to the pattern as the *Auslautverhärtung*, which may translate best as "syllable final fortition".

2) An Auslautverhärtung in Notker's dental stops

When discussing Notker's Anlautgesetz, and so the reduction of lenis#fortis contrast syllable initially, many scholars see hints of a similar process syllable finally. Analyses focus on the dental stops, and in recent decades have been primarily published by Penzl, Moulton, Lahiri/Kraehnemann, and Page.

2.1) Syllable final dental stops after vowels and liquids

After vowels and liquids ([l] and [r]), all scholars show that the /d#t/ contrast in stops is held. However, some see the contrast diminishing.

2.1.1) Penzl and Moulton

Penzl has written at least four publications handling Notker's Anlautgesetz.¹¹ In his 1968 work, he contrasts /d#t/ word finally

¹⁰ For more examples, see SPN02. pp. 22-24.

¹¹ Penzl, Herbert (1955).

Penzl, Herbert (1968). "Die Phoneme in Notkers Alemannischem Dialekt". *Germanic Studies in Honor of Edward Henry Sehrt*. Coral Gables: University of Miami Press. pp. 133-150.

Penzl, Herbert (1971). *Lautsystem und Lautwandel in den althochdeutschen Dialekten*. München: Hueber.

Penzl, Herbert (1983). "Notker's "Anlautgesetz" and Generative Phonology". *American Indian and Indo-European Studies*. Berlin: de Gruyter. pp. 441-448.

after vowels and liquids, citing the <d> in tôd 'death' versus the <t> in tôt 'dead'. However he also cites one example where the /d/ is usually written <d>, but also sometimes <t>, after the liquid in fêLd and fêLt 'field'.¹²

Moulton is more systematic, and breaks out dental stops by preceding sonorant and position in the word. Entries 8 - 10 in his grid¹³ are:

Num.	Env.	Lexeme /d/	Gloss	Lexeme /t/	Gloss
8	V()#	<u>éid/éit</u>	'oath'	<u>bréit</u>	'wide'
9	l()#	<u>uuáld/uuáLt</u>	'forest'	<u>geuuáLt</u>	'power'
10	r()#	<u>nórd/nórt</u>	'north'	<u>uuórt</u>	'word'

He then concludes:

“in the three word-final positions (positions 8, 9, 10), spellings with *t* rather than *d* are unusually numerous. This suggests that the opposition lenis≠fortis was being eliminated in these positions (though in fact this has not generally happened in modern Swiss German).”¹⁴

2.1.2) Lahiri/Kraehnemann and Page

Lahiri/Kraehnemann¹⁵ provide counts of word final <d≠t> in Notker's translation of Martianus Capella. Of more interest here however would

¹² Penzl (1968). p. 146.

In this quote, and in others to follow, the underlining and bolding of affected graphs are not in the original, as also are often not the vowel diacritics.

¹³ Moulton (1979). p. 244.

¹⁴ Moulton (1979). p. 245.

¹⁵ Lahiri, Aditi; Kraehnemann, Astrid (2004). "On Maintaining and Extending Contrasts: Notker's Anlautgesetz". *Transactions of the Philological Society* vol. 102, p. 4.

The authors propose a singleton≠geminate contrast in stops, rather than lenis≠fortis one.

be Page's critique of that analysis, which also provides his counts¹⁶ on how often word final /d/ was written <d> or <t>.

Lexeme	WGmc. source	<d>	<t>
<u>éid</u> , - <u>éit</u> ›oath‹	* <i>p</i>	5	1
<u>tôd</u> ›death‹	* <i>p</i>	59	0
<u>sîd</u> ›since ADJ PREP CONJ‹	* <i>p</i>	187	1
<u>góld</u> , <u>gólt</u> ›gold‹	* <i>p</i>	13	6
<u>uuáld</u> , <u>uuált</u> ›forest‹	* <i>p</i>	4	2
<u>nórd</u> , <u>nórt</u> ›north‹	* <i>p</i>	1	1
<u>uuárd</u> ›become 1 SG PRET‹	* <i>p</i>	35	3
<u>uuárd</u> ›become 3 SG PRET‹	* <i>p</i>	250	20
<u>bréit</u> ›wide‹	* <i>d</i>	0	3
<u>geuuált</u> ›power‹	* <i>d</i>	0	78
<u>uuórt</u> ›word‹	* <i>d</i>	0	125

Page first quotes Moulton's insight that:

"Notker's occasional use of <t> for reflexes of WGmc. **p* word-finally as suggesting the possibility of final fortition."¹⁷

¹⁶ Page (2013). p. 526.

Page's counts come from:

Sehrt, Henry; Legner, Wolfram (1955). *Notker-Wortschatz*. Halle: Niemeyer.

Moulton also uses this work for his examples. One senses that the source for Kraehnemann's counts must be:

Firchow, Evelyn (1999). *Die Hochzeit der Philologie und des Merkur: diplomatischer Textabdruck, Konkordanzen und Wortlisten nach dem Codex Sangellensis 872*. Zurich: Olms.

This book, or actually an earlier draft of it, was also the source for the counts in SPN00, back in 1989. Before publication, pre-prints of these were available to University of Minnesota students, where Firchow taught and where Kraehnemann was a graduate student. At the 1999 publication, the data were available in Adobe pdf on compact disc. In the late 1980's however, the data were printed off an IBM mainframe, in 128-bit EBCDIC encoding, on green-bar paper, which is what the author used to do manual counts in SPN00.

To view examples of these printouts, see:

Firchow, Evelyn; Gilmour, Stephen (1978). "Towards an Analysis of Notker Labeo's Old High German." *Computers and the Humanities*. vol. 12, pp. 81-88 (especially the examples on pp. 84-86).

The impact of Firchow's work is hard to overstate, and might be best seen in the Luxner (2013) review of Anlautgesetz scholarship, where so many of the cited authors either taught at or attended the Germanic Philology program at the University of Minnesota in the 1980's and 1990's, a program she founded with Cecil Wood.

¹⁷ Page (2013). p. 246.

Then Page draws on his letter counts to offer a finer grained analysis:

"Notker is more likely to use <t> for reflexes of WGmc. *þ in clusters of /l/ or /r/ plus coronal stop. The data suggest that the word-final contrast between fortis and lenis coronal stops was more salient after vowels than after /l/ and /r/."¹⁸

2.2) Syllable final dental stops after nasals

After nasals, for syllable final dental stops, scholars see a collapse of lenis≠fortis contrast,¹⁹ with only fortis appearing. A frequent

Moulton (1979). p. 245.

See also an earlier work:

Page, Richard (1999). "On Notker's Anlautgesetz". *Interdigitations. Essays for Irmengard Rauch*. New York: Peter Lang. pp. 305-309.

¹⁸ Page (2013). p. 246.

¹⁹ We have been talking about fortition both syllable initially and syllable finally, comparing where scholars see a lenis≠fortis contrast. A careful reader however may be wondering about that third location in a syllable, syllable medially. Here, however, syllable structure constraints combine with Notker's fortition rule to make all obstruents fortis.

Some discussion may be warranted. In all languages, an obstruent cannot appear syllable medially, unless bordered by another obstruent. Moreover, in Notker, lenis obstruents can only remain lenis when bordered on both sides by sonorants.

To illustrate, take for example Notker's [gánts] *ganz* 'whole', which would be traditionally posited phonemically as /gants/. Here any lenis or lenited dental stop in a hypothetical */gands/ would be subject to fortition because of the bordering [s], giving [gánts] rather than *[gánds].

Say perhaps that we replace that obstruent [s] with a sonorant, like [m] in a hypothetical */gandm/, written as *<gándm> representing *[gánd.m] or (with an epenthetic schwa added) *[gánd.əm]. Here note that the sonorant created a second syllable, and the dental stop [d] is now syllable final, not syllable medial.

The creation of this second syllable is due to the link between sonority and syllables. Sonority is not just a binary feature, but also a gradated one.

Syllables break into mountains of sonority, as in English *strengths* [streŋps]. Here the syllable nucleus peaks at the vocalic (and so highest) sonority of the [ɛ], ramping down to the left and right with the consonantal (and so lower) sonority of the [r] and [ŋ], and flattening out to the further left and right with the non-sonorant obstruent strings of [st] and [ps].

For the link between sonority and syllable structure, see:

Selkirk, Elisabeth (1984). "On the Major Class Features and Syllable Theory". *Language Sound Structure: Studies in Phonology*. Cambridge: MIT Press. pp. 112-117.

example cited would be Notker's <nt> alternation with <nd>, in the nominative singular and plural for 'hand' *hánt*, and *hénde*.²⁰

2.2.1) Penzl and Moulton

Penzl notes the collapse of contrast syllable initially and finally, but does not specify fortition.²¹ Instead, citing Jellinek's paper,²² he posits an underlying fortis /t/ here that undergoes lenition word medially:

"in der nach *n* im Sprechtakt das Fortisphonem *t* durch das entsprechende Lenisphonem *d* ersatz wurde."²³

Word medially, Moulton contrasts /d#t/ in *uuánda* 'because' against *sánta* 'sent'.²⁴ However, Jellinek sees here a singleton#geminate contrast, "das *tt* von **santta*",²⁵ which are understood in this paper as [wán.de] contrasting with [žánτ.te].²⁶ In any case, Moulton does not posit contrast after nasals word finally.

²⁰ Any analysis of syllable final dental stops should first start by extracting out a separate process syllable initially, a lenition, where the /d#t/ contrast merges to [d] after a homorganic nasal.

So, for example, in the Tatian (a text from a more northern dialect of Old High German, called Old East Franconian), the infinitives for 'find' and 'bind' contrast <d> and <t> in *findan* and *bindan*. However in Notker's Old Alemannic, the two words are both written with <d>, in *binden* and *uinden*.

Jellinek was the first scholar to identify this process:

Jellinek, Max (1935). "Bermerkungen zum Notkertext". *Zeitschrift für deutsches Altertum und deutsche Literature*. vol. 72. pp. 84-87.

He draws upon an analysis of Notker's Psalms by Wardale:

Wardale, Elisabeth (1893). *Darstellung des Lautstandes in den Psalmen Notkers nach der Sankt Galler Handschrift*. Zürich: Hertford.

²¹ Penzl (1968). pp. 148-149.

Penzl (1971). pp. 97,104.

Lahiri/Kraehnemann (2004). p. 41 (fn 24).

²² Jellinek (1935).

²³ Penzl (1968). p. 149.

²⁴ Moulton (1979). p. 245.

²⁵ Jellinek (1935). p. 86.

²⁶ A small, upper case T, so [τ], is used to mark either [d] or [t], when the principle of "Posit as Little as Possible" (SPN01 pp. 16-18) allows us to not specify the stop for fortition. In Notker's Old Alemannic, single vowels in unstressed syllables have a three-way contrast [ɪ#e#ʊ] when the syllable is open (i.e. ends in

2.2.2) Lahiri/Kraehnemann and Page

The analysis of Lahiri/Kraehnemann takes some additional explaining, but ends up relatable to that of Penzl and Moulton, in that dental stops are not contrasted after nasals. Lahiri/Kraehnemann propose a singleton≠geminate contrast rather than a lenis≠fortis one. In general, their singleton stops [p,t,k] correspond to the lenis [b,d,g] of Penzl, Moulton, and Page, and their geminate [pp,tt,kk] to the fortis [p,t,k] of the those other scholars.²⁷

Word finally, the situation is more complex. Lahiri/Kraehnemann do see Notker using <b,d,g> to mark singletons here:

"The alternative option, which we prefer, is that Notker had no FORTIS/LENIS contrast and hence no question of anything like *Auslautverhärtung*, and always used 'voiced' letters²⁸ for labials, velars and coronals word finally when they were singleton, but <t> for the geminate."²⁹

For word final <nt> however, <t> marks a singleton [t]:

"Notker had no contrast between final /nd/ and /nt/"³⁰

"Lack of contrast led Notker to write <nt> for a non-geminate"³¹

Page, in a paper opposing the Lahiri/Kraehnemann singleton≠geminate contrast, nevertheless references their remarks on the distribution after nasals:

the vowel), like in [wín.dɪ]). However that collapses to just [ə] when the syllable is closed (i.e. ends in a consonant), like in [wínɾ.təɾ].

²⁷ See the two tables laid out by Page (2013) p. 518.

²⁸ By "voiced letters", Lahiri/Kraehnemann are referring to Notker's pronunciation of Latin <b,d,g>. They see Notker as perhaps bilingual in Latin and Old Alemannic (2004) p. 5 (footnote 3), in contrast with Moulton (1979) p. 243, but in agreement with Penzl (1955) p. 207. See also Lahiri/Kraehnemann (2004) p. 13, along with Page (2013) p. 525, for additional comment on Notker's Latin and his Latin borrowings.

²⁹ Lahiri/Kraehnemann (2004) p. 43.

³⁰ Lahiri/Kraehnemann (2004) p. 41.

³¹ Lahiri/Kraehnemann (2004) p. 41.

"Note that Notker regularly used <nt> for all word-final clusters of nasal plus coronal stop (Lahiri/Kraehnemann 2004, p. 41)."³²

After nasals, word medially, Lahiri/Kraehnemann see the same singleton#geminate contrast that Jellinek refers to in "das *tt* von **uuinttar*".³³ They contrast the dative singular of 'wind' *uuinde* with the nominative singular of 'winter' *uuinter*, which are understood in this paper as contrasting [wín.dɪ] with [wínt.tər].³⁴

2.2.3) Additional attempts to establish syllable final [nd#nt]

What follows is just some due diligence - three attempts to establish an [nd#nt] contrast syllable finally. In the end, none of them is conclusive.

2.2.3.1) Word final <nd>

The simplest approach to establishing [nd#nt] syllable finally would be to just list all the instances of <nd> written word finally. Ideally, there would be many examples. In addition, they would all follow the pattern of referencing a Germanic */p/, so Old Alemannic /d/, like for example **múnd* for *múnt*, the original */p/ for which can still be seen in its Modern English gloss and cognate 'mouth'.

Unfortunately, that is not the case. The Notker-Wortschatz³⁵ lists only seven examples of word final <nd>.

³² Page (2013). p. 526.

³³ Jellinek (1935). p. 86.

³⁴ Lahiri/Kraehnemann (2004) p. 41.

³⁵ The Notker Wortschatz cites forms against an earlier indexing, based on the late 19th century Notker editions by Paul Piper. For example, Sehart cites <álechúnd> as I, 393, 26. That directs us to find the word in Piper's first book, page 393, on line 26. Later editions follow an Nx11122 indexing, where N=Notker, x=text (ex: p=Psalms, b=Boethius), 111=manuscript page, and 22=manuscript line. In Appendix A, where the bulk of forms are listed, both indexes are provided.

<álechú <u>nd</u> >	'all knowing'	uninflected	I, 393, 26
<pl <u>í</u> nd>	'blind'	uninflected	I, 298, 21
<ch <u>í</u> nd>	'child'	nom sg	II, 179, 14
<séh <u>e</u> nd>	'see'	2nd pl pres	II, 259, 16
<ferstá <u>nd</u> >	'understand'	3rd sg pres subj	II, 240, 7
<túg <u>e</u> nd>	'virtue'	acc sg	II, 235, 19
<b <u>í</u> nd>	'be'	2nd pl pres	II, 341, 27

Moreover, they do not all come from a Germanic */p/ (Old Alemannic /d/). For example, *plínd* 'blind' references Germanic */d/ in */blínda-/, which would have shifted to Old Alemannic /t/.

2.2.3.2) Word medial <nm>

A second path would be to look inside of words. Penzl, Moulton, Lahiri/Kraehnemann, and Page all write about contrasts word finally. The Spelling Patterns of Notker series however differentiates the syllable boundary from the word boundary. The former is the base phonological boundary (conditioning speech rules), while the latter is the base graphological boundary (conditioning spelling rules).³⁶

Of course, word initial is syllable initial and word final is syllable final.³⁷ The interesting environment is word medial, where the dental

³⁶ As sonority is gradated, so are both boundaries gradated. A syllable plus word boundary is a stronger speech boundary than just syllable, a word plus chapter-heading boundary would be a stronger spelling boundary than just the space between two words. See SPN01, pp. 22-25.

³⁷ This assumes that Notker did not elide words together while writing, as he almost certainly did during conversational speech. Notker spoke aloud (or had a reader speak aloud to him) when he wrote down his words, or else we would not see Anlautgesetz (or more accurately, the rule's inhibition). In addition, it may be that diacritics were added afterwards, perhaps during a second reading aloud. However, during that first reading aloud, the process of putting words to parchment would have greatly slowed the pronunciation of words. You need only play with even a 19th century quill and inkwell to get a feel for this. Penzl addresses this issue in 1955, and draws on a few spelling patterns to state: "Man könnte in einem Falle annehmen, daß sich auch bei Notker ein Unterschied zwischen dem überwiegend losen Anschluß in der Wortfuge und dem ausnahmslos engen Anschluß in der Morphem- und Silbenfuge." Penzl (1955) p. 209.

stop might be in the beginning, end, or middle of a syllable. These thoughts are not new. Back in 1935, Jellinek references them in his analysis of the lenition of /t/ to [d] by [n], when the /t/ is syllable initial even though word medial. He cites forms like *indêrêt*, from a lexeme typically written as *int+êrên*, to show:

"Auf verschiebung der silbengrenze beruht es, wenn das ursprünglich auslautende t das präfix int- vocal zu d wird."³⁸

Clausing³⁹ cites several scholars, going back to the 19th century, who find examples of Anlautgesetz word medially, even in the name Notker itself - *nôt + qér*, literally 'spear in need'. Penzl begins his 1955 treatment of Anlautgesetz with "Wechsel im Wort- und Silbenanlaut zu beobachten".⁴⁰

Attention is usually on the "im Anlaut" for scholarship over Notker and his Anlautgesetz. However, the same principle can be used when searching for spellings word medially, yet "im Auslaut".

When searching for a syllable final, word medial [nd≠nt] contrast, one pattern worth discussing is pointed out by Wardale,⁴¹ the <nm> of the lexeme *mánmende* 'gently'. The first half of this form would be a relic of Germanic */man**p**-/.

This author would agree with Penzl, but will also sketch out a path later on in the paper, whereby a careful reader could investigate whether words elided into each other, and so whether word boundaries are always syllable boundaries.

³⁸ Jellinek (1935). p. 86.

The author would mark this shift in syllable boundary as [ə̃n.dé:re:t].

³⁹ Clausing, Stephen (1979). "Notker's "Anlautgesetz"". *The Journal of English and Germanic Philology*. vol. 78 No. 3. pp. 358-373.

A main source for Clausing, who he cites, is:

Wilkins, Friedrich (1891). *Zum hochalemannischen Konsonantismus der althochdeutschen Zeit*. Leipzig: Fock. pp. 33-39.

⁴⁰ Penzl (1955). p. 197.

⁴¹ Wardale (1893). p. 51 (fn. 3).

The */nþ/ would have realized as /nd/ in Old Alemannic where the dental stop is syllable initial, as in the lexemes: *mándag*, *mándunga*, maybe *mánde*lchôsôn and, with primary umlaut of the /a/ to /ä/, in *ménden* and *méndî*. All of these are glossed with variations of 'gentle', 'peaceful', or 'joyful'.⁴² As detailed in an earlier footnote, sonority constraints on syllables would force a [ndm] in *mánmende* to put the [d] syllable finally in [mánd.mən.dɪ], while in the other spellings, like *mándeg*, the [d] would begin a syllable [mán.dĕg].

Moreover, as Old Alemannic */mánd/ does not appear as a stand-alone noun, it would have been less likely to undergo a possible analogical leveling of Germanic */nþ/ with Germanic */nd/. That is, this analysis works even if we allow Germanic */nd/ (Old Alemannic /nt/) in Notker's *múnt* and *múndes* 'mouth' (Germanic */munþ-/) to level to the Germanic */nd/ (Old Alemannic /nt/) in Notker's *lánt*, and *lándes* 'land' (Germanic */land-/). An Old Alemannic */mánd/, buried in just *mánmende*, could have escaped that process unnoticed.

Given the above thoughts, this word medial <nm> spelling could be used as an argument against the conclusion of the earlier four scholars. An <nm> marking [nd.m] in *[mánd.mən.dɪ] could contrast with an <ntm> marking [nt.m] in *múntmán* *[múnt.màn] 'ward', and both with [n.d] in *múndes* [mún.dəʒ] 'mouth', allowing contrast in dental stops syllable finally after nasals.

⁴² An alternate etymology for just *mánmende* is 'caressingly', relating the root to a word for Indo-European 'hand', and positing a cognate with Classical Latin *manus*. However that alternate etymology, maybe */manub/, still posits Germanic */nþ/ (Old Alemannic /nd/), so would not affect our analysis here.

Wardale would disagree with the above logic. Instead, she follows the neo-grammarians tradition of keeping pronunciation close to spelling, arguing that the Old Alemannic [d] here has simply disappeared over time, and that <nm> just marks [nm] (or even [mm], when spelled so):

"Assimilation of Germ. *d* to the corresponding nasal before *m*, has taken place in *manmindi*, 33, (21); *manmende*, 33, 3; *gemanmendest*, 93, 13; or more fully to the labial nasal in *mammendi*, 5 times, 44, 5 etc.; *mammende*, 5 times, 85, 5, etc.; *mammenden* 36,11; 75, 10; *manninte*, 24(10).⁴³

SPN01 argues that nasals in Notker assimilate in place before a homorganic obstruent.⁴⁴ Wardale's conclusion would be harder, if we could also show that nasals also assimilated in place before other nasals.

This was the case earlier in the history of Notker's language, as *ném~~men~~* 'name' and *stím~~ma~~* 'voice' come from earlier morphemes with /mn/ instead of /mm/.⁴⁵ Supporting this would be the rarity of <nm>. The sequence only occurs, when morpheme medial,⁴⁶ in *mán~~m~~ende*, again a morpheme that otherwise always spells out with the [d] marked, as in *mán~~d~~ag* and *mén~~d~~en*.

Inserting a [d] between the [n] and [m] would take care of the exception to nasal assimilation before nasals. The other <nm> spellings across morphemes, usually in compound nouns like <nm> in *ében~~m~~âze* 'of equal measure', could be explained as just a conservative spelling. That is, the spelling might have been <nm> even though

⁴³ Wardale (1893). p. 51 (fn. 3).

⁴⁴ SPN01, pp. 86-91.

⁴⁵ That earlier nasal-to-nasal assimilation was in the opposite direction, [mn] -> [mm].

⁴⁶ The form appears, in Notker's day, to be understood as *mán~~m~~* + *ende*, so as a present participle.

pronunciation was [mm], as how Modern German *einmal* is so often pronounced with [mm].

However a Latin borrowing, with the reverse sequence of <mn> rather than <nm>, argues that Notker did not assimilate nasals before other nasals, but only before obstruents. Derivatives of Latin *damnatio* 'damnation' occur twice in his Psalms. Both show an unassimilated <mn>, marking [mn].

<ferdám <u>mn</u> ônt>	'damn'	3rd pl pres	II, 398, 14
<ferdám <u>mn</u> unga>	'damnation'	nom sg	II, 164, 25

Without nasal assimilation in place before other nasals, Notker's pronunciation of <nm> in *mánnmende* could mark either [nd.m] or [n.m], and so cannot be contrasted against *múntmán* to conclusively establish [nd≠nt] syllable finally.

2.2.3.3) Word medial <nt≠ntt>

There are no sequences of <dd>, <dt>, or <td> after either <m> or <n> in the *Sehrt Wortschatz*. Moreover, after <m>, there are no instances of <tt>.

However, we do see three instances of <tt> after <n>, all in compound words.

<há <u>nttu</u> âlôn>	'hand washing' (of Pontius Pilate)	dat pl	II, 56, 5
<scá <u>ntt</u> ôd>	'shameful death' (of Christ on the cross)	acc sg	II, 362, 21
<úr <u>stántt</u> ách>	'resurrection day'	nom sg	II, 74, 12

All three second elements start with Germanic */d/ (Old Alemannic /t/), which should not mean much, as they would be [t] regardless due to the Anlautgesetz. More interesting is that all three of their

first elements also end with Germanic */d/ (germ. */skamda-, handu-, stand-/), which again is realized as Old Alemannic /t/.

So there is a pattern. Could this <ntt> marking [nt.t] in *scánttôd* *[škánt.tò:d] 'shameful death, nom sg', contrast with <nt> marking [nd.t] in *sánta* *[žánd.tɛ] 'send, 3rd sg past'? And then both also contrast with <nd> marking [n.d] in *hénde* [hán.dɪ] 'hand, nom pl'?

Perhaps, but it could also just be a spelling convention. The <ntt> lexemes are in compound words, so do not form good minimal pairs with *sánta* and *hénde*, where the second element is just an inflectional ending. That is, Notker might have just written <ntt> in *scánttôd* because he recognized *scánt* and *tôd* as two different words. And he wrote *sánta* with one <t> as it looked like one word, similar to *uuínter*. All three could have been pronounced [nt.t].

Such a conclusion would be reinforced by another potential <ntt> compound, *hánt* 'hand' plus *tât* 'deed' [hánr.tâ:t]. This is spelled just <nt>, even though it references a Germanic */d/ (Old Alemannic /t/) in the first element.

<há <u>nt</u> tâte>	'handwork'	acc pl	II, 57, 10
<há <u>nt</u> tâte>	'handwork'	nom pl	II, 57, 11

Notker creates many compounds to help his students understand Latin. Nevertheless, the word for 'handwork' sounds like an Old Alemannic term in common use. The other three read as if compound words manufactured in the monastery, to express theological concepts. If so, that would explain the <tt> in the first three forms, as Notker was just writing together two words to make a new one, rather than sounding out the commonly used term for 'handwork'.

In any case, these <ntt> spellings are not enough to establish syllable final [nd#nt].

2.2.3.4) Neither contrast nor collapse established

Note that this review only shows that we cannot establish an [nd#nt] contrast syllable finally. Nevertheless, that does not mean that it shows:

- 1) That a speech rule, like syllable final fortition, eliminated this contrast.⁴⁷
- 2) Or that any remaining syllable final /nd/ had already merged with /nt/, due to analogy. An argument for that would be that syllable initial /n.t/ and /n.d/ already merged to [n.d] via lenition. For example, in the conjugation of *uínden* 'find, inf' and *bínden* 'bind, inf', the dental stop would only appear syllable finally, and so could only differ, in two forms - 1st and 3rd singular past **uánd* and *bánt* and 2nd singular imperative **uínd* and *bínt*. Everywhere else, the dental would have been syllable initial and [d].
- 3) Or the reverse, that all these words really end in [nd], and are just written <nt> word finally. That is, maybe dental lenition applies to the stops even syllable finally. Spelling alternations like *int-* vs *ind-* in *índêrêt* 'dishonor, inf' and *íntlâzêt* 'release, inf' argue against that. However, the <nt> and <nd> here are in complimentary distribution.
- 4) Or that *hánt* and *lánt* really do end differently in Old Alemannic, the first [nd] and the second [nt], along with *uánt* and *bánt*. There could be a spelling rule that spells all these as <nt> word finally.

⁴⁷ Here the author breaks from his 1996 analysis in SPN01. pp. 72-79.

5) Or that more than one of these processes is at work.

2.2.3.5) And we get little help from Notker's Latin

A final thought might be to look at recent Latin borrowings.⁴⁸ As can be gleaned from earlier examples from Moulton, and will be spelled out in a later quote from Page, these recent borrowings were restoring contrasts that had been lost due to the Old High German Consonant Shift.⁴⁹

The Latin word for 'cloak', *mantellum*, is borrowed into Notker's Old Alemannic in two forms.

<mántellîne>	'little cloak'	dat sg	I, 695, 26
<gemántelôte>	'cloaked'	past part masc nom pl	I, 844, 11

Note that neither comes in with *<nd>, as *mándellîne or *gemándelôte. This indicates that Notker pronounced Latin *mantellum* as [mánr.təl.ləm], so not with the single [t] of Latin, which would have lenited to [d] in Old Alemannic, but with the geminate of his Old Alemannic. Moreover, the above form has the second dental stop syllable initial, not syllable final, so is not really our focus here.

Maybe we just need to flip open a Latin dictionary, and make two lists – a first list for Latin words ending in <nd>, and a second list for

⁴⁸ As may be laid out in a later paper in the SPN series, the author believes that Latin borrowings into Old Alemannic are better understood if we delineate between Classical Latin, Vulgar Latin, and Ecclesiastical Latin. It is from Ecclesiastical Latin that he sees *mantellum* being borrowed.

⁴⁹ Not all scholars agree with this logic. For example, see a later publication by Aditi Lahiri, this time co-authored with Kennard, Holly: Kennard, Holly; Lahiri, Aditi (2019). "Nonesuch phonemes in loanwords" *Linguistics* vol. 58 issue 1. pp. 83-108.

Their introductory sentence is "Borrowed words alone should not introduce new phonemes – this is the central claim of this paper." Kennard/Lahiri (2019). p. 83.

Latin words ending in <nt>. Afterwards, we could see which words from both lists were borrowed into Notker's Old Alemannic, and compare how they were spelled. Sadly, this proposal will not work, as one list will remain empty. No Latin words end in <nd>, not even when all of the possible inflectional endings are included. In Latin, <nd> is never written word finally, only <nt>.⁵⁰

3) Establishing contrast beyond the dental stops

As for the labial and velar stops, both Moulton⁵¹ and Page⁵² cite examples of a word medial (and generally syllable initial) lenis≠fortis contrast after vowels and liquids.

Graph	ǃ__V	ǂ__V	N__V	l__V	r__V
	<i>síben</i> >seven<	<i>âbent</i> >evening<	<i>úme</i> >around<	<i>sélbêr</i> >self<	<i>stérben</i> >die<
<p>, <pp>	<i>síppa</i> >relation<	<i>scâpâre</i> >sheepskin<	<i>gúmpiten</i> >pond<	<i>álpôn</i> >Alps<	<i>górpotôn</i> >bodies<
<g>	<i>régen</i> >rain<	<i>frâgên</i> >ask<	<i>síngen</i> >sing<	<i>fólgên</i> >follow<	<i>mórgen</i> >morning<
<k>, <kk>	<i>rúkke</i> >back<	<i>cóukele</i> >trickery<	<i>cínken</i> >prong<	NF ⁵³	<i>fúrkûn</i> >trident<

The /b≠p/ and /g≠k/ contrasts were rebuilding in Old Alemannic, after the Old High German Consonant Shift had almost wiped them out, as new Latin words with /p/ and /k/ were getting borrowed in (ex: *fúr**k**ûn* in the above table, borrowed from Ecclesiastical Latin *furca*). Page goes on at length about this pattern.

"One may assume that the sounds represented by <p> and <k,c> in this environment are loanwords from Latin, such as *gór**p**otôn* from L. *corp*us >body< *fúr**k**ûn* from L. *furca* >fork<, where Notker consistently uses a single graph representing a fortis stop for

⁵⁰ This will become significant later on in the paper.

⁵¹ Moulton (1979). p. 245.

⁵² Page (2013). p. 523.

⁵³ NF stands for Not Found. The table is from Page, but includes some forms listed earlier by Moulton.

the sound that corresponds to a voiceless stop in the Latin source word. Therefore, Notker's dialect appears to have extended the fortis-lenis distinction"⁵⁴

Moulton does not provide examples of <p> or <g> word finally. Page, when reviewing data from Lahiri/Kraehnemann, quotes them:

"Note that there are no instances of the letter <p> or the letters <k/c> being used in final position."⁵⁵

Analyses of Notker's obstruents have traditionally focused on the Anlautgesetz, and so traditionally on stops, often on just word initial stops. For example, fricatives are not in the lists developed by Moulton and Page. To lay the groundwork for a deeper analysis, perhaps a first step would be to extend the grids of Moulton and Page, so that we establish contrasts across:

- 1) The three rows of obstruents: labials, dentals and velars.
- 2) The five obstruents in each row: both stops, both fricatives, and the one affricate (ex: /b#p#v#f#pf/).⁵⁶
- 3) The four types of preceding sonorant - vowels, followed by the less sonorant liquids (but still give an entry for both /l/ and /r/, as Moulton and Page do), followed by the still less sonorant nasals (only one, as nasals assimilate in place to a following obstruent in Notker).

⁵⁴ Page (2013). p. 525.

As mentioned earlier, the bolding and underlining are not in the original quotes, but added by the author, as are vowel diacritics.

⁵⁵ Lahiri/Kraehnemann (2004). p. 17.

Page (2013). p. 525.

⁵⁶ Affricates and geminates (ex: /pf/, /pp/) are treated as sequences of two phonemes here, rather than as a single, separate phoneme. Moreover, the /h/ is understood as a laryngeal, so not lenis nor velar nor even a fricative. In addition, the fortis /x/ could easily be pronounced as a uvular /χ/, as in Swiss German. Nevertheless, to simplify classification terminology, both are lumped into the velar obstruent row here.

4) The four combinations of syllable boundary (the base boundary for speech rules) and word boundary (the base boundary for spelling rules): word initial and syllable initial, word medial and syllable initial, word medial and syllable final, word final and syllable final.⁵⁷

Multiplying these together gives $3 * 5 * 4 * 4 = 240$ entries, which are listed in Appendix A.

The Spelling Patterns of Notker series sees all of Notker's obstruents contrasting, when the obstruent is preceded by a sonorant. Exceptions to this are minor:

- 1) The collapse of syllable initial /d#t/ to [d] after [n].
- 2) The substitution of either [x] or [θ] for /h/, when the laryngeal is bordered by a consonant (within the same syllable).
- 3) The collapse of lenis#fortis to just fortis, when obstruents are in a cluster (again, within the same syllable).

4) A shared conditioning for Notker's fortitions

Whether this was Page's intention or not, his earlier grid (from section 2.1.2) breaks out examples by gradation of sonority of the previous sonorant. Below his grid is pasted back in, with three rows

⁵⁷ Technically, there should be nine environments - the three syllable ones (initial, medial, final) multiplied by the three word ones (initial, medial, final). However, five of these drop out. All three syllable medial environments are inherently fortis, per the combination of Notker's fortition rule and the sonority constraints on syllables detailed in an earlier footnote. Moreover, the two remaining environments (word initial plus syllable final, word final plus syllable initial) would both be impossible combinations, so tautologies. Nevertheless, that conclusion assumes, as quoted from Penzl in an earlier footnote, that Notker spoke while writing with "dem überwiegend losen Anschluß in der Wortfuge", and that this slowed his speech so that words did not elide into each other.

added. These are in bold, and are summaries. They calculate the effect of the previous sonorant on the marking of fortition.

Lexeme	WGmc. source	<d>	<t>
<u>éid</u> , - <u>éit</u> ›oath‹	* <i>p</i>	5	1
<u>tôd</u> ›death‹	* <i>p</i>	59	0
<u>sîd</u> ›since ADJ PREP CONJ‹	* <i>p</i>	187	1
Totals, plus percentage of Notker's /d/ (Gmc */p/) written fortis <t>, after vocalic sonority.	2/253 1%	251	2
<u>gól<u>d</u></u> , <u>gól<u>t</u></u> ›gold‹	* <i>p</i>	13	6
<u>uuá<u>d</u></u> , <u>uuá<u>t</u></u> ›forest‹	* <i>p</i>	4	2
<u>nó<u>d</u></u> , <u>nó<u>t</u></u> ›north‹	* <i>p</i>	1	1
<u>uuá<u>r<u>d</u></u></u> ›become 1 SG PRET‹	* <i>p</i>	35	3
<u>uuá<u>r<u>d</u></u></u> ›become 3 SG PRET‹	* <i>p</i>	250	20
Totals, plus percentage of Notker's /d/ (Gmc */p/) written fortis <t>, after liquid sonority.	32/335 10%	303	32
<u>br<u>éit</u></u> ›wide‹	* <i>d</i>	0	3
<u>geuuá<u>t</u></u> ›power‹	* <i>d</i>	0	78
<u>uuó<u>r<u>t</u></u></u> ›word‹	* <i>d</i>	0	125
Totals, plus percentage of the reverse, as a control group to indicate data quality.⁵⁸	0/206 0%	0	206

As Page remarks, and was quoted earlier:

"Notker is more likely to use <t> for reflexes of WGmc. **p* in clusters of /l/ or /r/ plus coronal stop. The data suggest that the word-final contrast between fortis and lenis coronal stops was more salient after vowels than after /l/ and /r/.⁵⁹"

⁵⁸ Note what is essentially a control group for this statistical analysis – the marking of Germanic */d/ (Alemannic /t/) in the reverse way, as lenis <d>. Out of 206 forms, there are no mistakes, so zero free variation, which is a positive indicator of the accuracy of the previous two calculations. Of course, Notker's texts are not perfectly transcribed, but their level of data quality is remarkable for vernacular texts of the Middle Ages. Indeed, within the Germanic corpus, Notker's works stand out as both very large and very carefully spelled, making them the preferred works for statistical analyses.

⁵⁹ Page (2013). p. 246.

As detailed in an earlier footnote, sonority is not just a binary feature in phonology, where [+son] is the opposite of [-son].⁶⁰ It is also gradated along a scale. One proposed sonority scale for English is:

[a] > [e o] > [i u j w] > [r] > [l] > [m n ŋ].⁶¹

Perhaps such a fine-grained sonority scale was significant in Notker's speech. From Notker's written documents, however, this author has only been able to substantiate a more basic scale:

⁶⁰ It shares this trait with vowel height (high, mid, low) and place of articulation (labial, dental, palatal, velar, uvular, laryngeal) - two concepts that also translate so awkwardly into binary feature combinations.

⁶¹ Selkirk (1984). p. 112.

If front rounded vowels were added, this would also work for Modern German and Notker's Old Alemannic.

In addition, Selkirk's sonority scale goes on into the obstruents, but those degrees do not affect fortition in Notker. Significantly, Notker's obstruents become fortis in isolation. See Moulton (1979) pp. 249-250. They do not need a neighboring obstruent to trigger the process, and so are unaffected by a neighboring obstruent's level of sonority. Sonority only affects fortition in that a preceding sonorant can inhibit the process, if both sonorant enough and close enough to the following obstruent.

Gradations in distance from the preceding sonorant also affect the inhibition of fortition. Provisional gradations in distance might be:

- 1) Together in a syllable. All syllable final examples (and inherently, syllable medial ones) fall here. The remaining distances only come into play when the obstruent is syllable initial.
- 2) Separated by a syllable boundary (in polysyllabic roots and roots followed by inflectional endings).
- 3) Separated by a syllable boundary, where an unstressed prefix precedes a stressed root. Notker's spelling rules consider these (and the next environment) to be word boundaries.
- 4) Separated by a syllable boundary, where a stressed prefix precedes a stressed root, or two between two stressed roots in a compound word.
- 5) Separated by a traditional word boundary - the space following a single root or compound plus its final inflection.
- 6) Separated by a word boundary plus space plus low point.
- 7) Separated by a word boundary plus space plus high point.
- 8) Separated by a word boundary plus space plus paragraph or chapter heading.

Glosses (those Old Alemannic words written above Latin ones) would need to be reviewed individually, to determine if they were pronounced in isolation or as part of a string.

vowels > liquids > nasals⁶².

That is, a preceding sonorant of vocalic sonority inhibited Anlautgesetz more frequently than a sonorant of the lesser liquid sonority, which itself inhibited Anlautgesetz more frequently than a sonorant of the even lesser nasal sonority. The pattern held across the three gradations of boundary analyzed: syllable plus space (defined as a word boundary), word boundary plus low point, and word boundary plus high point.⁶³ The pattern also held across language, whether the preceding sonorant was in a Latin or an Old Alemannic word.⁶⁴ It held across place of articulation (labial, dental, velar) of the obstruent.⁶⁵

Coincidentally, it is this same gradation of sonority (vowels > liquids > nasals) that can also be seen in the conditioning of Auslautverhärtung in Page's grid.

The Anlautgesetz and Auslautverhärtung are both fortitions, the former syllable initial, the latter syllable final. If the two processes can be shown to have the same conditioning, then these two processes could be joined into a single fortition rule.⁶⁶ That would be exciting, because for two centuries⁶⁷ the two processes have been treated separately, whether in the Braune or Schatz grammars, or in a variety of publications.⁶⁸

⁶² See SPN00. pp. 177-180, and 180-183 on how obstruent sonority does not matter.

⁶³ SPN00. pp. 177-180.

⁶⁴ SPN00. pp. 174-175.

⁶⁵ SPN00. pp. 175-177.

⁶⁶ Moreover, if they can be joined, they should be joined, per the guidelines in SPN01 on simplifying systems. See SPN01 pp. 40-41.

⁶⁷ Coincidentally, the year of this paper's posting, 2022, marks the bicentennial of Grimm's first description of the process, back in 1822.

⁶⁸ An exception would be:

What would also be exciting would be the conditioning itself. If Notker's syllable final fortition was also dependent on the level of sonority of a previous sonorant, that could provide us a model for how syllable final fortition could have entered into other German dialects. That is, between 900 and 1100, some speakers of High German dialects may have said [bur.gə, burk] 'town', while still saying [ta.gə, tag] 'day'.

Alternatively, the pattern could even argue that Old Alemannic was a source for Middle High German final fortition. A fortition gradated by sonority could have generalized as it spread to other dialects, and there lost its complexity.⁶⁹ In Middle High German

Iverson, Gregory; Salmons, Joseph. "Glottal Spreading in Germanic" (1999). *Linguistische Berichte*. vol. 178. pp. 135-151.

The scholars link Notker's Anlautgesetz to German final fortition:

"progressive sandhi-level spread is attested from Notker's records in Old High German and reported down to the present. Thus, an initial lenis appears fortis after a fortis obstruent."

"For Old High German, this strongly suggests that Notker's dialect evinced rightward spread across word boundaries, a pattern also long reported in some Upper German dialects (e.g. Braune/Eggers 1987:101). These data provide historical support for the notion that [spread glottis] is actually present in German finals (p. 22 in the downloadable document in Academia.edu, see also the summary on p. 24).

For an expansion of the Iverson and Salmons argument above, see:

Iverson, Gregory; Salmons, Joseph (2007). "Domains and directionality in the evolution of German final fortition". *Phonology*. vol. 24 pp. 1-25.

Pages 16-17 also cite 19th century dialect studies, some of you can also read in Clausen (1979).

This author's analysis is more in line with Moulton (1979) pp. 249-250, where Notker's obstruents become fortis in isolation (so by default, without the need for progressive assimilation). However, he does agree with Iverson's and Salmon's "progressive sandhi-level spread" and with their insight that joins both Anlautgesetz and Auslautverhärtung into a single process. He only differs in that he sees that spread as coming from a preceding sonorant and in inhibiting fortition.

⁶⁹ While, as earlier cited by Moulton, retained its complexity in Swiss German dialects. Moulton (1979) p. 245.

For the theory of phonological rules generalizing (i.e. starting out complex, and getting simpler as they spread over time and/or place), see:

Kiparsky, Paul (2003). "The Phonological Basis of Sound Change". *The Handbook of Historical Linguistics*. Edited by Joseph, Brian; Janda, Richard. pp. 311-342.

texts, or at least in our normalized editions, we see a much simpler fortition than in Notker. All obstruents become fortis syllable finally, while none do syllable initially. Then again, that simpler system of final fortition is at least partially just text editing, as recently remarked on by Iverson and Salmons:

"A look into the history of Auslautverhärtung provides key support for its origins in prosodic marking and, at the same time, reveals a rich set of competing systems which continue down to the present day across the dialects, thus informing our understanding."⁷⁰

As with so many patterns in philology, one could draw many multiple conclusions here, not all compatible with each other.

4.1) Auslautverhärtung across obstruent and preceding sonorant

To investigate this line of reasoning, below is a summary of syllable final fortition in Notker, with the detail provided in Appendix B. The columns mark the three gradations of sonority (vocalic, liquid, nasal) of the preceding sonorant. The rows list the six lenis obstruents that follow the sonorant. The cells can then mark the percentage of time that the lenis phoneme was written with a fortis graph. An example would be where a /d/ was written as <t>, as in Page's counts of *uuáLt* for /wald/ 'forest', where we would normally expect *uuáLd*. For most cells, the marking of fortition is blocked. For clarity, where the reason is the same as to the left, just '-----' is written.

⁷⁰ Iverson/Salmons (2007). p. 15.

Fortition	Vowels	Liquids	Nasals
/b/ -> [p]	2%	4-17%	40%
/d/ -> [t]	2-4%	12%	Spelling Rule ⁷¹
/g/ -> [k]	Spelling Rule {5%}	---- {9%}	---- ⁷² {12%}
/v/ -> [f]	Spelling Rule	----	---- ⁷³
/ž/ -> [s]	Phonemes not merged	----	----
/h/ -> [x]	Spelling Rule and Phonemes not merged	----	----

4.2) Alternative conclusions

As is likely already obvious to the careful reader, the author believes that the data show a shared conditioning in Notker's fortitions. That is, both Notker's Anlautgesetz and his Auslautverhärtung can be merged into a single process, Notker's Verhärtung. However that is not the only conclusion that can be drawn. What follows are some initial alternatives.

4.2.1) Perhaps there are too few forms to define patterns

Even if a careful reader agrees with the author's conclusion, that reader may differ on the strength of the conclusion. For some cells, there are just so few forms. For example, take Page's citation again of *uuált* for /wald/ 'forest', where we would normally expect *uuáld*. That would fall into the cell of syllable final /d/ after liquids written as fortis <t>. This will have value of 12% (quite near the

⁷¹ Fortition is not marked because Notker only writes <nt> word finally, not also <nd> there, mirroring a Latin spelling pattern.

⁷² A spelling rule blocks the marking of fortition ([g] and [k] are both marked <g> word finally). However, this rule is breaking down, especially in the Psalms, and an unweighted percentage is provided in brackets.

⁷³ A spelling rule blocks the marking of fortition. Both [v] and [f] are written <f> word finally, mirroring Latin spelling patterns. However, after nasals, epenthesis before [f] is marked, where <nf#mf> marks [mv#mpf], allowing us to infer fortition. Unfortunately, the data are limited to one morpheme, and explainable in too many other ways.

10% in Page's sampling). There are 420 examples of syllable final /ld/ and /rd/, and 53 of them marked as <lt> or <rt>. This feels like a decent amount of data from which to draw a pattern.

But then drop to the cell for /v/ after nasals. As is detailed in Appendix B, this range is based on just two morphemes - /vinv/ 'five' and /žanvt+j/ 'soft'. And one could argue that the morpheme for 'soft' was really /žanft+j/ by Notker's day, so would not qualify, leaving just the word for 'five'.

4.2.2) Perhaps we are seeing a regressive inhibition of fortition

Another idea would be that the variations below have little to do with the sonorant preceding with obstruent, but with the sonorant following it. For example, in the *Sehrt Wortschatz* we see that Notker wrote <p> for /b/ in /xrunb/ 'crooked'.

<chrú <u>mp</u> >	II, 105, 25
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However, this word does not come from the main text, but is written as a gloss (i.e. translation) over the Latin word *camur* 'crooked'.⁷⁴ That means <chrúmp>⁷⁵ here was pronounced in isolation, without a following

⁷⁴ To see this, one needs to go beyond the word listings in the *Sehrt Wortschatz*, and look up the word in an edition of Notker's works. Currently, the quickest way to do that is to search the web for "Titus Notker Psalms" or "Titus Notker Boethius". Then within that manuscript, do a word search for "chrump". A more full featured search tool is ANNIS. To find that, search for "ANNIS Deutsch Diachron Digital". The Firchow editions are also digitized (in DVD, available with the paper book at University libraries), along with the King and Tax series (available for purchase from de Gruyter, in both electronic and paper form). In addition, the Piper editions are now past copyright, so posted to the public domain.

⁷⁵ The author has normalized diacritics across this paper, as their variation can be distracting. The reality however is messier. The gloss here is actually spelled without any accent, as are most glosses. The Firchow editions highlight how often the vowel diacritics are not written, or written over the off-glide vowel, or even over consonants.

syllable. Nevertheless, when the word occurred in the main text and was followed by a sonorant, then the scribe wrote .

<chrú mb . unde>	II, 105, 25
<chrú mb in>	II, 126, 13
<chrú mb uuâren>	II, 169, 29
<chrú mb . Et>	II, 382, 21

Perhaps Notker's fortition is not inhibited progressively (by a preceding sonorant), but rather regressively (by a following sonorant). The punctuation in two of these examples argues against that. However, there are thousands of such forms with lenis obstruents syllable finally, and the lead is worth investigating.

4.2.3) A shift in syllable boundary, due to elision

Yet another thought is that the above examples with /xrú**nb**/ could also point to elision across words. That is, could the in <chrú**mb** . unde> not mark [xrú**mb**.ún.dɪ], but instead [xrúm.**b**ún.dɪ]. Again, the punctuation argues against that conclusion for this particular example. Nevertheless, if one were to catalogue the many examples of this pattern, perhaps elision could be substantiated.

4.2.4) Regressive fortition by a following obstruent

For yet another idea, we can revisit the morpheme for 'five'. Sehart finds 14 examples with <nf> word finally.

<f ínf >	I, 66, 26; 162, 14; 197, 28(2); 339, 25; 699, 4; 729, 20; 750, 13; 751, 10
<u ínf >	I, 489, 4
<f únf >	II, 424, 7; 429, 11(2); 482, 17 ⁷⁶

⁷⁶ Left out of these alternatives would be that we are looking at different speech and spelling rules across different manuscripts. Notice how Notker writes <u> for the /i/ in /v**ím**v/ 'five' several times here (<f**únf**> instead of <f**ínf**>). Penzl sees that as maybe rounding the /i/ to [ü] when surrounded by labial consonants. Penzl (1968). p. 137.

And in all of these, the graph combination <nf> does not mark an epenthetic [p] (which is written <mf>, often alternating with <mpf>). Epenthesis would be triggered by a fortis [f], as the rule inserts a fortis stop between a homorganic nasal and a fortis fricative. We only see epenthesis marked in one form, where the /v/ is followed by an obstruent, and one in close juncture, as it begins an inflectional ending.

<taz fímfta . únde>	I, 48, 25
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Could this fortition be triggered by the following obstruent [t] (perhaps only when in close juncture, as in an inflectional ending)? If so, we could be looking at a regressive fortition.⁷⁷

4.2.5) And down the rabbit hole we go

Alternatively, is it even more complex than that? Should [ft] be an allowable syllable onset in Notker? This does not quite follow the guidelines from Benware for dividing syllables in Modern German (and which were adapted in SPN01 for Notker).⁷⁸ But if Notker could

Nevertheless, what really jumps out in the above citations is that this spelling is only found in the Psalms (citations prefaced with II, to mark Piper's second book). We may have no manuscripts that Notker himself wrote, but we do have some that scholars believe were only one or two copies away from his original. The Psalms, however, are seen as several copies removed. Could a <u> for [ü] in <funf> mark the dialect of one of those later copyists? SPN01 and SPN02 argue that scribes only mark phoneme mergers (SPN01. pp. 35-39; SPN02. pp. 24-26). In that case, maybe we are seeing a difference in phoneme inventories over time. For many generations of Old Alemannic speakers, /ü/ was not a separate phoneme. However, that changed in a certain generation. Could that generational change in phoneme inventories have happened in between Notker's composition and a later copying? If one accepts that, sounds like [ü], [ö], and [æ] could have been allophonic when Notker wrote his Consolation of Philosophy, but phonemic when this last scribe copied down his Psalms. The author is not yet advocating this, but the theory is sure a lot of fun.

⁷⁷ Recall an earlier quote on "dem ausnahmslos engen Anschluß in der Morphem- und Silbenfuge".

Penzl (1955). p. 209.

⁷⁸ SPN01. pp. 125-131.

pronounce [št] syllable initially as in stân 'stand, inf', is it unreasonable to think that he could also begin a syllable with [ft]? Both sequences are a fricative followed by [t]. After all, American and German learners of Russian have little difficulty with a word like Вторник 'Tuesday', pronounced [ftór.nɪk]. If so, perhaps the second <f> in <taz fímfta . únde> really marks a syllable initial [f] due to Anlautgesetz, in [fúmp.fta].

On the other hand, maybe the scribe just spoke a little quickly here, perhaps anticipating the reduction in Modern Swiss dialects, and dropped the word down to a single syllable [fúmpft]. Then the second <f> would mark [f] from fortition in a syllable medial obstruent cluster.

Similarly, did Notker just elide the second vowel of 'fifth' in <taz fímfta . únde> into the beginning of a next word, which also begins with a vowel? The above would then be [fúmpf.tún.dɪ]. Again, here of course there is punctuation between the two vowels, which would argue for a pause between the two words. Nevertheless, there are other such sequences to examine, most without punctuation.

To borrow a frequently quoted phrase from Lewis Carroll's "Alice's Adventures in Wonderland", it is easy, far too easy, to "go down the rabbit hole" when interpreting Notker's spelling patterns. It is difficult to come to any conclusions without also finding alternative conclusions, and then finding both exceptions (and maybe exceptions to the exceptions) to both one's conclusions and their alternatives. So

Benware, Wilbur (1986). *Phonetics and Phonology of Modern German*. Washington D.C.: Georgetown Press. p. 85.

it is with uncertainty and humility that the rest of this section is offered.

4.3) Walking through the grid

In this section, we will walk through the grid - the three gradations of sonority before each of the six lenis obstruents.

Some cells will have only one process - fortition. An example again would be where syllable final /d/ is written <t> after liquids, as in Page's counts of *uuáLt* for /wald/ 'forest', where we would normally expect *uuáLd*.

These are the easy ones.

Other cells will introduce a second process, perhaps a spelling rule, which Notker used to make his writing look more like Latin, as in <f> word finally in *uuóLua* and *uuóLf* 'wolf', instead of *uuóLua* and **uuóLu*. There is a help here though. Spelling rules can give themselves away by showing an absolute calculation, like "100% fortition" (i.e. always *uuóLf*, never **uuóLu*).⁷⁹

For other cells, that "second process" is not technically a process, but just the reality that the lenis and fortis obstruents differ in more than fortition. A fortition then would not merge the phonemes, and so would not be marked.⁸⁰ Again though, here we are given a help. These can also give themselves away by showing another absolute, like "0% fortition". For example, Notker writes hundreds of examples of

⁷⁹ Of course, many phonological processes are absolute. However, in SPN00, fortition via the Anlautgesetz was shown to be gradated.

⁸⁰ See SPN02. pp. 22-24, and SPN01. pp. 35-39.

the words for 'until' and the personal pronoun for '1st person dat pl', glossed and cognate with English 'us'. Nevertheless, the count of /unž/ [únž] uns 'us' being written as fortis unz is zero.⁸¹

On top of these, we will sometimes see a third or fourth process. Analogy was sketched out, in section 2.2.3.4, as a possibility for <nt>, while the difficulties with <nf/mf> have already been detailed. Moreover, there may be weakening going on in velars syllable finally, where stops reduce to fricatives, fricatives to an aspirate, and the aspirate to zero. Sometimes the author will attempt to untangle these multiple processes, but sometimes not. Once we reach three or four processes in a spelling pattern, it gets hard to distinguish analyses from just flailing around in that rabbit hole.

4.3.1) /b/ written fortis syllable finally

Latin allows both and <p> word finally (ex: sub 'under' volup 'desire'). This argues against a spelling rule here that could mask contrasts, or at least against one after vowels. For the counts, <bh,p,ph> are scanned for as fortis spellings of /b/.⁸²

⁸¹ Moreover, as a control, that zero is equal to the count of the reverse, where /uns/ [únts] unz 'until' is written zero times as lenis uns.

⁸² A careful reader may be wondering how comprehensive and accurate the counts are. Well, the answer is simple. They are neither comprehensive nor accurate, at least in the mathematical senses of those words. They are simply a good faith effort.

Perhaps some discussion is warranted.

The author is not a professional academic, but just a simple hobbyist. He paid a few dollars to a book binder to scan the Notker Wortschatz into a pdf, then exported that pdf to a spreadsheet, and matched that to the DVD in the Firchow edition concordance: Firchow, Evelyn (2008). *Notker der Deutsche von St. Gallen: althochdeutscher und lateinischer Wortindex zu den Übersetzungen von Aristoteles De interpretatione und Categoriae, Martianus Capellas De nuptiis Philologiae et Mercurii und Boethius De consolatione Philosophiae*. New York: Olms-Weidmann.

In doing so, his admiration for both the Firchow and Sehart works has only grown, as they match up 99.9% of the time. One needs to of course include the dozen pages of Wortschatz corrections, at the end of:

Sehart, Henry (1962). *Notker-Glossar*. Tübingen: Max Niemeyer Verlag.

4.3.1.1) Vocalic sonority plus /b/

Notker provides 22 morphemes of syllable final /b/ after vowels.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/gr ab /	<u>gráb</u>	'grave'
/a b /	<u>ab</u>	'from'
/žtr ab /	<u>stáb</u>	'staff'
/h ab /	<u>háb</u>	'have'
/g eb /	<u>géb</u>	'give'
/di eb /	<u>dîeb</u>	'thief'
/li:b/ b /	<u>lîb</u>	'life'
/li eb /	<u>lîeb</u>	'dear'
/wi:b/ b /	<u>wîb</u>	'woman'
/žkre jb /	<u>scréib</u>	'write'
/žwe jb /	<u>swéib</u>	'circle'
/tre jb /	<u>tréib</u>	'drive'
/žki:b/ b /	<u>skîb</u>	'push'
/he b /	<u>héb</u>	'lift'
/lo:b/ b /	<u>lôb</u>	'praise'
/true b /	<u>trûob</u>	'anxious'
/ue b /	<u>ûob</u>	'practice'
/lew b /	<u>lôub</u>	'leave'
/lew b /	<u>lôub</u>	'leaf'
/rew b /	<u>rôub</u>	'rob'
/žrew b /	<u>stôub</u>	'dust'
/tew b /	<u>tôub</u>	'deaf'

From these, ten forms end in a fortis graph.

All the forms cited and counted are listed in Appendix B, so that a reader can review, challenge and revise the populations and calculations for their own analysis. The author fully expects these counts to be corrected, and welcomes those corrections, and will periodically update this draft paper with them, and credit those doing that work.

In addition, the author believes that this field is moving towards centralized data stores, as in ANNIS. That would allow the author's data to be abandoned in favor of just queries against that centralized data. This is why he includes morpheme lists, to simplify that future querying.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<cráp>	neut acc sg	II, 221, 15
<gráp>	neut acc pl	II, 186, 21
<liēpsám>	uninflected	II, 356, 3
<kelóuplîh>	uninflected	I, 651, 12
<gelóuptôn>	3rd pl past	II, 551, 2
<beskîpte>	past part nom pl masc	I, 452, 11
<zestóupta>	3rd sg past	II, 120, 3
<getrûoptiu>	past part nom sg fem	I, 823, 30
<ûopta>	3rd sg past	I, 300, 29
<geûoptêr>	past part nom sg masc	I, 695, 18

Next to those 10 are 536 forms with /b/, giving a fortition rate of 2%. The detail is in Appendix B (tabs ab, eb, ib, ob, and ub), with the fortis forms highlighted in red.

4.3.1.2) Liquid sonority plus /b/

As will be a pattern throughout this analysis, there are far fewer forms after liquids than after vowels. Nevertheless, Notker does provide nine morphemes of syllable final /b/ after /l/ or /r/.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/xal b /	chál b	'calf'
/xor b /	chór b	'basket'
/žal b /	sál b	'salve'
/žter b /	stér b	'die'
/žwér b /	suér b	'grab'
/wer b /	wér b	'turn'
/wel b +j/	wél b e	'round'
/hal b /	hál b	'half'
/žel b /	sél b	'self'

For the moment, ignore the last two morphemes, /hal**b**/ 'half' and /žel**b**/ 'self', and review results for just the first seven. In these

first seven, Notker's Old Alemannic has /b/ syllable finally 29 times, with five of those marked fortis.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<chál p >	acc sg	II, 313, 27
<chál p >	acc sg	II, 453, 28
<chál ph >	acc sg	II, 272, 11
<chó rp >	nom sg	II, 336, 7
<irstár pta >	3rd sg past	II, 263, 26

That gives a 17% fortition rate. Following the pattern after vocalic sonority, this 17% is quite close to the 10% that Page found for dental stops after liquid sonority.⁸³ The detail is in Appendix B (tab Nb,lb,rb), with the fortis forms highlighted in red.

Now we come to our first "second process". There are two additional forms with /b/ after a liquid.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/hal b /	<hál b >	'half'
/žel b /	<sél b >	'self'

The word for 'self' is written 34 times with the /b/ syllable finally, more often than the previous seven words combined. In addition, none of these ends in a fortis graph, all end in . Moreover, the word for 'half' occurs three times more than that, 102 times, with only two of those ending in a fortis graph.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<hál p >	acc sg	II, 474, 8
<ánderrhál p >	acc sg	II, 330, 17

⁸³ Note also that these five forms are all in the Psalms (Sehrt citations beginning with 'II', so in Piper's second book). This will be a recurring theme as we look through the tables. The consistency of Notker's Boethius spellings breaks down by the Psalms (or maybe our copy of a copy of a copy of a copy), allowing phonological processes to more easily peak through.

When these are added in, the pattern still holds. Notker still writes /b/ as fortis after liquids over twice as often as after vowels. However, it is just 4% of the time, seven out of 165, rather than 17% of the time.

In the beginning of this section, we talked about additional processes, beyond just fortition, and perhaps we are seeing one here. It is the author's belief that Notker wrote some words down so often that he started to memorize their spellings. Otherwise, it is difficult to explain the great variation in spellings for words that rarely occur, versus the minimal variation in those that often occur. For examples of the latter, just flip open the Notker Wortschatz to the entry for *daz* 'that, pronoun nom/acc sg neut, also as conjunction'. There are pages of examples, without variation. Alternatively, look up *dánne* 'then', and see hundreds of examples, only two with the variant *dénne*.⁸⁴ Similar is *uuánda* 'because', again with hundreds of examples, and only one as *uuánde*.

Was this also partially the case with *hálb* and *sélb*? That is, the scribe ended these in not because he heard [b], but because he had written them with so many times before. Maybe, although the words are not nearly as common as *daz* or *dánne*. In recognition of this uncertainty, both the 4% and 17% fortition rates are listed in the grid. A statistical investigation here would make a nice paper, comparing word spelling variation with word frequency.

⁸⁴ As always in Notker, there is the exception to the exception. Although *daz* and *dánne* seem to have a spelling that is regularized via memorization, their initial <d> does follow Anlautgesetz, giving the familiar alternates of *taz* and *tánne*.

4.3.1.3) Nasal sonority plus /b/

Returning to task, we next look at fortition after the lowest level of sonority, that of nasals. Here there are only three morphemes.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/xru nb /	<chrú mb >	'crooked'
/la nb /	<lá mb >	'lamb'
/tu nb /	<tú mb >	'dumb'

These occur 15 times syllable finally, and six of those times the /b/ is spelled <p> (ex: *Lámp* instead of *Lámb*), giving a 40% fortition rate after nasal sonority.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<chrú mp >	uninflected	II, 105, 25
<gechrú mp ta>	1st sg past	II, 197, 3
<gechrú mp te>	past part nom pl masc	I, 750, 23
<lá mp >	acc sg	II, 239, 9
<lá mp >	nom sg	II, 329, 25
<tú mp lích> ⁸⁵	uninflected	II, 265, 3

The detail is in Appendix B (tab Nb,lb,rb), with the fortis forms highlighted in red.

4.3.2) /d/ written fortis syllable finally

Next, we will revisit Page's counts in the dentals. Latin allows both <d> and <t> word finally (ex: *apud* 'among', *et* 'and'). This argues against a spelling rule here that could mask contrasts, or at least against one after vowels. For the counts, <dh,t,th> are scanned for as fortis spellings of /d/.

⁸⁵ Although onsets can be maximized to make the labial stop syllable initial here, the syllable division rules in SPN01 (pp. 125-131) keep it syllable final.

4.3.2.1) /d/ after vocalic sonority

After vowels, Notker ends syllables with /d/ 1,037 times, and ends them with a fortis graph 45 times, giving a fortition rate of 4%. The forms are too numerous to list in the paper, but are provided in Appendix B (tabs ad,ed and id,od,ud). The fortis forms are highlighted in red.

4.3.2.1.1) The ending /o:d/

What jumps out is how 23 (so half) of these 45 fortis spellings are for where we would normally expect to see <ôd> for /o:d/, especially where that <ôd> is a noun suffix. The sequence /o:d/ only ends 10% of all spellings of /d/ after vowels, just 103 of the 1,037. As 23 of these 103 are marked <ôt>, that would give a fortition rate after long /o:/ of over 20%. That feels odd, so perhaps there another process at work.

A clue comes from digging into the data, where we see that these <ôd> affixed nouns are usually paired with an <ôn> affixed weak verb, a 2nd class (ô-stem). Two examples would be:

/germɪn/ 'enchant'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/o:t/ suffixed verb	ends in [o:t]	<gérmenô <u>t</u> >	past part/ 3rd sg pres Not Found
/o:d/ suffixed noun	ends in [o:d]	<gérmenô <u>d</u> >	nom sg I, 783, 3
/o:d/ suffixed noun	maybe still ends in [o:d], and just spelled <ôt> on analogy with the verb ending.	<kérminô <u>t</u> >	nom sg II, 37, 17

/niww/ 'renew'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/o:t/ suffixed verb	ends in [o:t]	<geníuuu <u>ô</u> t>	past part II, 92, 12
/o:d/ suffixed noun	ends in [o:d]	<níuuu <u>ô</u> d>	nom sg Not Found
/o:d/ suffixed noun	maybe still ends in [o:d], and just spelled <ôt> on analogy with the verb ending.	<níuuu <u>ô</u> t>	nom sg II, 92, 13

Would these common <ôt> verb endings have caused some confusion with spelling the <ôd> noun suffix?⁸⁶ If so, and if the <ôd> forms are pulled out, the fortition rate drops to 2%, so equal to that for vowels before labials. To reflect this, both this adjusted 2%, along with the original 4%, are included in the main grid.

4.3.2.1.2) The contraction <chít>

The form *chít*, a variant of *chidet* 'say, 3rd sg pres' is worth calling out, as it occurs hundreds of times, and would severely skew the calculations if included. However, this does not look like an example of /d/ becoming fortis after a vowel. Although *chít* reflects [xít], phonemically it would be /xid+e+t/. The form looks to be a contraction, with the <t> reflecting the second dental stop, the /t/ in the inflectional ending.

⁸⁶ If so, a similar confusion could account for the higher count of *tô*t spellings for *tô*d 'death, nom sg', as the same concept is written with <t> on the end in the adjective, *tô*t 'dead, nom sg masc'.

4.3.2.2) /d/ after liquid sonority

Notker provides 16 morphemes of syllable final /d/ after /l/ or /r/.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/bil <u>d</u> +j/	bí <u>l</u> de	'image'
/bal <u>d</u> /	bá <u>l</u> d	'bold'
/val <u>d</u> /	uá <u>l</u> d	'fold'
/vel <u>d</u> /	ué <u>l</u> d	'field'
/gol <u>d</u> /	gó <u>l</u> d	'gold'
/hal <u>d</u> /	há <u>l</u> d	'inclined'
/hol <u>d</u> /	hó <u>l</u> d	'trusted'
/žkul <u>d</u> /	scú <u>l</u> d	'guilty'
/tul <u>d</u> /	tú <u>l</u> d	'festival'
/wal <u>d</u> /	uuá <u>l</u> d	'forest'
/wil <u>d</u> /	uuí <u>l</u> d	'wild'
/er <u>d</u> /	é <u>r</u> d	'earth'
/her <u>d</u> /	hé <u>r</u> d	'hearth'
/nor <u>d</u> /	nó <u>r</u> d	'north'
/wer <u>d</u> /	uué <u>r</u> d	'worth'
/wer <u>d</u> /	uué <u>r</u> d	'become'

Across these 16 morphemes, Notker's Old Alemannic has /d/ syllable finally 447 times, with 54 of those marked fortis.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<bá <u>l</u> t>	uninflected	II, 393, 4
<fé <u>l</u> t>	2nd sg imp	I, 44, 12; 90, 22
<gó <u>l</u> t>	nom sg	I, 247, 4 II, 59, 19
<kó <u>l</u> t>	nom sg	I, 88, 27 II, 441, 2
<gó <u>l</u> tfáreuen>	dat sg masc wk	I, 196, 9
<gó <u>l</u> tcríeze>	dat sg	I, 196, 8
<hó <u>l</u> t>	uninflected	I, 122, 32; 862, 9 (Ruodp. Brief)
<hó <u>l</u> tlichemo>	dat sg neut	I, 40, 26
<scú <u>l</u> t>	nom sg	I, 326, 12
<scú <u>l</u> théizen>	gen sg	I, 739, 14
<scú <u>l</u> théizzôn>	dat pl	II, 395, 8
<uuá <u>l</u> t>	acc sg	I, 87, 20 II, 346, 1
<uuá <u>l</u> tpóuma>	nom pl	II, 405, 6
<uuí <u>l</u> tstócche>	dat sg	II, 405, 8
<é <u>r</u> tpibôth>	acc sg	II, 120, 2
<nó <u>r</u> t>	nom sg	II, 368, 28
<nó <u>r</u> thálb>	uninflected	II, 369, 1, 2
<unuué <u>r</u> t>	uninflected	I, 163, 21
<uué <u>r</u> t>	uninflected	II, 58, 27
<uué <u>r</u> tlichûn>	dat sg fem wk	I, 351, 25
<uué <u>r</u> tsámôt>	past part	II, 81, 15
<uuá <u>r</u> t>	1st sg past	I, 141, 14 II, 136, 15; 307, 17
<uuá <u>r</u> t>	3rd sg past	I, 6, 14; 27, 4; 28, 8; 76, 1; 194, 30; 212, 18; 467, 25; 862, 11 II, 24, 1; 92, 11; 123, 17; 209, 16; 276, 22; 283, 25; 347, 2; 351, 9; 414, 16, 23; 471, 27; 544, 17

That gives a 12% fortition rate, slightly above the 10% in Page's sampling. The detail is in Appendix B (tab Nd,ld,rd), with the fortis forms highlighted in red.

4.3.2.2.1) The contraction <uuírt>

The form *uuírt*, a variant of *uuírdet* 'become, 3rd sg pres' is another form worth calling out. Like *chít*, it occurs hundreds of times, and

would severely skew the calculations if included. However also like *chít*, this is not an example of /d/ becoming fortis after a liquid, but another contraction. Although *uuírt* reflects [wírt], phonemically it would be /wird+e+t/, with the <t> reflecting the second dental stop, the /t/ in the inflectional ending.

4.3.2.2.2) Word medial <lt> and <rt>

There is an additional process here too, a spelling practice, which blocks us from seeing fortition before a dental preterite, where the /d/ in a root would have occurred word medially, yet still syllable finally.⁸⁷ Examples are limited to ja-stem weak verbs, where the dental preterite /t/ would append directly to the root, making the /ld/ or /rd/ syllable final.

That is, [ld.t] is written <lt> and not *<ldt>, merging its spelling with that of [lt.t] and [l.t]. Some examples should make this clearer. Consider the pattern for [ld.t] in the verb for 'fault'.

/žk <u>l</u> d/ 'fault'	Form	Spelled	Inflection
/gɪ+žk <u>l</u> d+jɛ+nn/	[gɪ.škú <u>l</u> .dən]	<gescú <u>l</u> den>	inf I, 321, 3
/gɪ+žk <u>l</u> d+t+ɛ/	[kɪ.škú <u>l</u> .tɛ]	<kescú <u>l</u> ta>	1st sg past II, 417, 21

Some similar lexemes would be:

/g <u>l</u> d/ 'gild'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/uber+g <u>l</u> d+jɛ+nn/	[úb.ər.gù <u>l</u> .dən]	<úbergú <u>l</u> den>	inf Not Found
/uber+g <u>l</u> d+t+ɪmʊ/	[úb.ər.gù <u>l</u> .tɪ.mʊ]	<úbergú <u>l</u> timo>	past part dat sg neut II, 171 14

⁸⁷ A careful reader will wonder why the author decided on a spelling rule here, rather than a speech one. It is due to a similar pattern already detailed after nasals (ex: *sénden* /NT+jɛ/, *sánta* /NT+t+ɛ/ 'send') and also mirrored in fricatives (*stérchen* /r(k)x+jɛ/, *stárhta* /rx+t+ɛ/) 'strengthen') and affricates (ex: *sézzén* /ats+jɛ/, *sázta* /ats+t+ɛ/ 'put').

/hald/ 'incline'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/gɪ+hald+je+u/	[kɪ.há <u>l</u> .dʊ]	<kehé <u>l</u> do>	1st sg pres II, 185, 6
/gɪ+hald+t+e/	[gɪ.há <u>l</u> .tɛ]	<gehá <u>l</u> ta>	1st sg past II, 528, 10
/gɪ+hald+t+imʊ/	[gɪ.há <u>l</u> .tɪ.mu]	<gehá <u>l</u> temo>	past part dat sg masc I, 730, 20

/huld/ 'soothe'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/huld+je+i/	[hú <u>l</u> .dɪ]	<hú <u>l</u> de>	3rd sg pres subj II, 185, 24
/gɪ+huld+t+e/	[gɪ.hú <u>l</u> .tɛ]	<gehú <u>l</u> ta>	3rd sg past II, 455, 23
/gɪ+huld+t+e:r/	[gɪ.hú <u>l</u> .tɛ:r]	<gehú <u>l</u> thêr>	past part nom sg masc II, 890, 2

This <lt> spelling for [ld.t] also spells [lt.t] in roots ending in /t/.

/galt/ 'compensate'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/ɪn+galt+je+nn/ ⁸⁸	[əŋ.gá <u>l</u> .tən]	<ingé <u>l</u> ten>	inf I, 293, 27
/ɪn+galt+t+e/	[əŋ.gá <u>l</u> .tɪ]	<ingá <u>l</u> te>	past part acc pl masc I, 261, 21

Moreover, this <lt> spelling marks an [l.t] from /llt/, along with an [l.t] from just /lt/. Consider the ja-stem verb for 'put', followed by a strong verb for 'push'.

⁸⁸ In this word, the original /ɾ/ on the prefix /ɪNT-/ would have been lost in Notker's speech, otherwise the /g/ would have been written <k> *[əŋɾ.kál.tən] *<in(t)kélten>, due to Anlautgesetz. However we do see the dental stop before other phonemes, either written as in <intháben> or inferred from the epenthesis before a fortis fricative, where the /v/ had been made fortis (due to Anlautgesetz or some similar predecessor rule) and reanalyzed as /f/ before Notker's time. Compare <geuáhen> I, 61, 19 with <inpfáhen> I, 397, 17, both infinitives for 'catch'.

/ʒʔa <u>ll</u> / 'put'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/ʒʔa <u>ll</u> +je+nn/	[ʃtá <u>l</u> .lən]	<sté <u>ll</u> in>	inf II, 52, 26
/gɪ+ʒʔa <u>ll</u> +t+e:n/	[gɪ.ʃtá <u>l</u> .te:n]	<gestá <u>l</u> tê<	past part dat pl II, 75, 24

/ʒka <u>lt</u> / 'push'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/vɪr+ʒka <u>lt</u> +n/	[vər.ʃká <u>l</u> .tən]	<uerscá <u>l</u> ten>	past part I, 34, 19

You see the pattern after /r/ too, although there are less examples.

/wí <u>rd</u> / 'value'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/wí <u>rd</u> +je+t/	[wír. <u>d</u> ət]	<uuír <u>d</u> et>	3rd sg pres II, 101, 9
/un+wí <u>rd</u> +t+o:n/	[un.wír. <u>d</u> .to:n]	<úuuír <u>th</u> ôn>	3rd sg past II, 455, 23

4.3.2.3) /d/ after nasal sonority

As <nt> forms a conjugation ending in Latin, Notker would have been quite familiar with the sequence ending a word. Examples would be *clamant* 'cry, 3rd pl pres', *trahunt* 'drag, 3rd pl pres', along with such common words as *sunt* 'be, 3rd pl pres' and *erant* 'be, 3rd pl past'.

However, Latin does not have words that end in <nd>,⁸⁹ and Latin is the source writing system for Old Alemannic.⁹⁰

Given that, per the guidelines of SPN01, it would be natural (though not required), for Notker to write both word final [nd] and [nt] as

⁸⁹ To verify, search for "online-latin-dictionary" and "ezglot". The latter is a tool geared towards enthusiasts for Scrabble and other spelling games. The former allows one to also search through inflections.

⁹⁰ The concepts of source and target writing systems are defined in SPN01 (pp. 47, 106-124), along with natural spelling rules.

<nt> in his target writing system of Old Alemannic. This is because his source writing system, Latin, did not contrast the graph sequences <nd> and <nt> word finally, but only wrote <nt>. This would leave the exact pronunciation of /nd/ here occluded, either [nd] or [nt], as laid out in section 2.2.3.4.

What reinforces a spelling rule here is the absoluteness of it. Word final nasal + dental stop occurs over one thousand times in Notker's works, and is spelled fortis 100% of the time. This is unlike in the labials, where syllable final /nb/ is written <mp> only 40% of the time. Indeed, that absolute 100% is unlike the previous five cells that we have researched (vowel before /d/, liquid before /b/, etc.). As argued at the beginning of this discussion, absolute patterns (whether 0% or 100%) argue for spelling rules, not gradated phonological processes.

Such a spelling rule also allows us to remove a rule ordering from SPN01, one that always felt unnatural to the author, where fortition is required to take place after epenthesis.⁹¹

4.3.3) /g/ written fortis

Notker's Ecclesiastical Latin needs two graphs for velar stops - one for lenis /g/ and one for fortis /k/. Instead, the language offers

⁹¹ SPN01. p. 134. The rule ordering after it should also go away, and dental lenition not be maximized (SPN01. pp. 80-85, but then then later reversed out syllable finally, by that older fortition rule, pp. 72-79). The author was never comfortable with any of that analysis. This would leave us with only natural word orderings (ex: nasal assimilation before epenthesis after an assimilated nasal), not contrived ones.

maybe six in <c,k,q,x,ch,g>. The reasons for this stretch back two millennia before Notker, and are worth a footnote.⁹²

⁹² The source alphabet for European scripts is the Phoenician alphabet. Prototypes of this were first used to write down northern and western Semitic languages (ex: Aramaic, Hebrew, Phoenician) by 1100 AD. The letters likely originally came from Egyptian hieroglyphs. As the Phoenicians were a maritime people, this script spread with their sailors and merchants across the Mediterranean.

Phoenician contrasted the letters <ʔ≠k≠q>, named as 'gīmel, kaph, qōph'. The original pictures were of a throwing stick (or camel), palm of the hand, and eye of a needle, and you can perhaps see that in the letters (ex: thread going through the needle eye in qōph <Φ>). These <ʔ≠k≠q> corresponded to the phonemes /g#k#q/. That last one is a uvular stop, a place of articulation that can be phonemic in some Semitic languages even today, like Modern Arabic.

Around 1000 AD, this Semitic alphabet was adapted to an Indo-European language, Greek, which did not have uvular consonants. However, Greek did contrast three rows of velar stops - voiced, voiceless, and aspirated, or /g#k#k^h/.

Spelling the first two was easy. Phoenician 'gīmel' <ʔ> for Phoenician /g/ was borrowed in as Greek 'gamma' <Γ,γ> for Greek /g/. Phoenician 'kaph' <κ> for Phoenician /k/ was adapted into Greek 'kappa' <Κ,κ> for Greek /k/. Note that we do not have a g-letter at this time. Instead, that <ʔ> 'gīmel' and <Γ> 'gamma' both resemble, and are the source for, our Roman letter <c>.

Returning to task, this still left the Greek aspirated stop /k^h/ to mark. The uvular 'qōph' <Φ> for /q/ was not adapted for this phoneme. Instead, the Greeks created a new letter, 'chi' <Χ,χ> for Greek /k^h/.

When saying 'Greek' above, we are really referring to the eastern Greek alphabet, also called the Ionic or Classical Greek alphabet. A western variant also developed, called the Euboean or Chalcidian Greek alphabet.

The Etruscans drew upon this western version. They lived in Italy, next to the early Romans, and began writing by 800 BC. Perhaps the Etruscans were in contact with Phoenician speakers and writers too. Regardless, this western Greek script retained the <q> (Phoenician 'qōph' <Φ>), and transmitted it to the Etruscans, in addition to their new <x> (Greek 'chi' <Χ,χ>), plus the <c> (Greek 'gamma' <Γ,γ>, Phoenician 'gīmel' <ʔ>), and the <k> (Greek 'kappa' <Κ,κ>, Phoenician 'kaph' <κ>). The Etruscans were offered four graphs.

However, Etruscan did not have a four-way contrast in stops, or even a three-way one like Phoenician and Greek. In Etruscan, there was just a two-way contrast, /k=k^h/, in many ways quite relatable to the two-way /g#k/ contrast found in Latin, English and German. And here, gentle reader, is the source of our misery. If only the Etruscans had done the sensible thing. They had two velar stop phonemes, and were offered four letters for them. Why not just adopt two letters and forget the other two? Instead, they kept all four.

For their /k/ phoneme, the Etruscans used three graphs - <c> before <i, e>, <k> before <a>, and <q> before <u> (there was no <o> in Etruscan). To a modern linguist, this looks like the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) symbols [c,k,q], which mark the palatal, velar and uvular voiceless stops, in allophonic distribution - the more front [c] before the front vowels [i,e], the middle [k] before the mid vowel [a], and the more back [q] before the back vowel [u]. For /k^h/, Etruscans adopted that Greek 'chi' letter, <x>.

Of these six graphs, only <c> occurs word finally in Latin, if you ignore <x> as [ks] in words like *rex* 'king' and the occasional <ch> at the end of Hebrew names like *Enoch*.

Regardless, Notker picks <g> to mark [g] word finally, and not <c>. Moreover, he also picks <g> to mark [k] word finally, even after obstruents. A good example would be the word for 'fish'.

Again, the Etruscans lived in Italy, and were neighbors of the early Romans. By 700 AD, this Etruscan alphabet was adapted to mark Latin. Similar to Etruscan, Latin contrasted two velar stops, although /g=k/ instead of the Etruscan /k=k^h/. However, the early Romans missed a second chance at house cleaning, and brought over all four of the Etruscan velar stop letters, <c,k,q,x>. The <c> was assigned to /g/ (or sometimes also /k/), the <k> to /k/, the <q> to /kw/ (when paired with <u>, technically <v>, as there is not a separate <u> from <v> at this time). That Etruscan <x> for /k^h/ was repurposed to mark Latin [ks], as in *rex* 'king'. Then things got even more convoluted. By 200 BC, <c> was also consistently marking Latin /k/ (or had always also marked /k/). In 230 BC, to bring clarity in teaching, Spurius Carvilius Ruga, the owner of a primary school, added lines to Latin <c> (or adapted Greek 'zeta', <Z,ζ>, as Latin had no /z/) to create a new graph, <g>. This new graph <g> would now mark Latin /g/, allowing <c> to fully replace <k> as /k/. However, that replacement does not fully take place, as Romans retained <k> for some archaic words, like *kalendae*, the plural for 'first day of the month'. This now left Latin with five velar stop graphs, <g,c,k,q,x>.

So at this point, why not add a sixth? As the Roman Empire expanded, it encountered Greek society. By 200 BC, Romans had adopted many Greek technical terms in philosophy, science, and medicine. Christianity also reached Rome via the Greek world by 100 AD, bringing religious words. Those terms beginning with Greek /g/ and /k/ were borrowed in with <g> and <c>. However, those beginning with Greek /k^h/ could not be spelled with <x> (Greek 'chi' <X,χ>), as that graph had already been brought in to mark Latin /ks/. Instead, the Romans develop a sixth graph, <ch>, to spell new Latin words like *Christus* for 'Christ' and *chirurgus* for 'surgeon'. Although some educated Romans may have pronounced these words with a Greek [k^h], that <ch> quickly became just another way to spell /k/ in popular speech.

Then the letter <c> stopped working, or at least as a reliable velar stop graph. By 400 AD, and likely several centuries before, spoken Classical Latin had been evolving into what we call Vulgar Latin, the predecessor of modern Romance languages like Italian, French, Spanish, and Romanian. In Vulgar Latin, the voiceless velar stop /k/ palatized before front vowels (spelled <i,e>) and the [e:] reflected in the spellings of <ae,oe>. The result was that although Latin now had six velar stop graphs to mark two velar stop phonemes, the most important one, <c> for /k/, no longer completely worked.

This is the pitiable plight faced by Notker, and other early medieval scribes in Western Europe, as they adapted the Latin alphabet to their vernacular languages.

/vižk/ 'fish'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/vižk/	[víšk]	<físg>	nom sg I, 167, 28

In Notker's Ecclesiastical Latin, <c> and <sc> were not always pronounced with a [k]. Instead, /k/ palatized before front vowels. We can infer this, as the scribe was careful to write <k> before front vowels in his Old Alemannic, even in the combination [šk]. Nevertheless, before a back vowel, <c> can be written. Again, continuing with the word for fish:

/vižk/ 'fish'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/vižk+iž/	[víž.kəž]	<fískes>	gen sg II, 540, 21
/vižk+in/	[víž.kən]	<físken>	dat pl I, 751, 23
/vižk+e/	[víž.ke]	<físca>	acc pl II, 243, 25
/vižk+u/	[víž.ku]	<físco>	gen pl I, 167, 27

Perhaps Notker avoided <c> word finally to avoid any hint of palatization, so that <físg> would be read as [víšk] and not *[víš]. Moreover, the monk may have avoided <k> there in the same way that he avoided <q> there, as neither occurred word finally in Latin. In any case, Notker has a spelling rule where all word final velar stops are written <g>, whether from /g/ or /k/.

/žang/ 'song'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/žang+iž/	[žán.gəž]	<sánges>	gen sg I, 126, 5
/žang/	[žánɡ]	<sáng>	nom sg I, 691, 25

/žtan(k)x/ 'scent'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/žtan(k)x+iž/	[štánk.xəž]	<stánches>	gen sg I, 708, 2
/žtan(k)x/	[štánk]	<stáng>	nom sg I, 291, 32

/vižk/ 'fish'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/vižk+e/	[víž.ke]	<fí <u>sca</u> >	acc pl II, 243, 25
/vižk/	[vížk]	<fí <u>sg</u> >	nom sg I, 167, 28

4.3.1.1) Vocalic sonority plus /g/

After vowels, syllable final /g/ is written <g> per the spelling rule, as is syllable final /k/.

/tag/ 'day'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/tag+in/	[dá <u>g</u> +in]	<dá <u>gen</u> >	dat pl I, 50, 7
/tag/	[tá <u>g</u>]	<tá <u>g</u> >	nom sg I, 45, 22

/bokx/ 'billy goat'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/bokx+in/	[bók.xən]	<bó <u>cchen</u> >	gen sg I, 708, 2
/bokx/	[pók]	<pó <u>g</u> >	nom sg I, 291, 32

However, the spelling rule is not absolute, as it was with dental stops following [n]. Notker does not write <g> 100% of the time. Instead, fortis graphs creep through, especially in the Psalms. After vowels, Notker ends syllables with /g/ 2,091 times, and ends them with a fortis graph 107 times, giving an unweighted fortition rate of 5%.

For the counts, <c,q,k,gh,ch,qh,kh,cch> are scanned for as fortis spellings of /g/. There is also an additional wrinkle, not seen with /b/ and /d/. Unlike with the labial and dental stops, some spellings replace /g/ with <θ>. These are kept in a separate group, as they may not reflect fortition.

After vowels, the forms are too numerous to list in this paper, but are provided in Appendix B (tabs ag, eg, ig, og, ug). The fortis forms are highlighted in red, while the few forms with <θ> are highlighted in purple.

4.3.3.2) /g/ after liquid sonority

Notker provides 12 morphemes of syllable final /g/ after /l/ or /r/.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/wal <u>g</u> /	<i>uuá<u>l</u>g</i>	'roll'
/bel <u>g</u> /	<i>bé<u>l</u>g</i>	'swell'
/vol <u>g</u> /	<i>uó<u>l</u>g</i>	'follow'
/žPu <u>l</u> g/	<i>spú<u>l</u>g</i>	'intend'
/ber <u>g</u> /	<i>bé<u>g</u></i>	'mountain'
/ber <u>g</u> /	<i>bé<u>g</u></i>	'hide'
/bu <u>g</u> /	<i>bú<u>g</u></i>	'town'
/žor <u>g</u> /	<i>só<u>g</u></i>	'sorrow'
/ar <u>g</u> /	<i>á<u>g</u></i>	'anger'
/hungir+e <u>g</u> /	<i>hú<u>ng</u>er<u>g</u></i>	'hunger'
/mar <u>g</u> /	<i>má<u>g</u></i>	'marrow'
/mu <u>g</u> /	<i>mú<u>g</u></i>	'short'

Across these 12 morphemes, Notker's Old Alemannic has /g/ syllable finally 194 times, with 18 of those marked fortis, and two without marking.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<úderbál <u>ch</u> >	acc sg	II, 221, 15
<úderbál <u>gh</u> >	acc sg	II, 108, 20
<pér <u>ich</u> kíbillla> ⁹³	nom sg fem	II, 454, 1
<búr <u>ch</u> >	nom sg	II, 102, 7; 130, 13
<púr <u>ch</u> >	nom sg	II, 224, 26
<búr <u>ch</u> >	gen sg	II, 318, 12; 324, 16
<búr <u>ch</u> >	dat sg	II, 473, 12 (2)
<búr <u>gh</u> >	dat sg	II, 482, 10
<púr <u>cl</u> iche>	nom pl fem	I, 100, 21
<púr <u>ch</u> líute>	nom pl	I, 660, 24
<ár <u>ch</u> >	acc sg	II, 288, 22
<érdpr <u>uch</u> > ⁹⁴	acc sg	II, 467, 24
<hómbér <u>ch</u> >	acc sg	II, 286, 4
<múr <u>0</u> fáriu>	acc pl neut	I, 281, 3
<múr <u>0</u> fára>	nom sg fem wk	I, 85, 12
<scántpúr <u>ch</u> >	nom sg	II, 242, 13
<uuártpr <u>uch</u> >	acc sg	II, 323, 9

That gives a 9% fortition rate, which is higher than the 5% rate for /g/ after vowels.

The two forms with <0>, <múr0fáriu> and <múr0fára>, point to a process other than fortition, and so are not counted here. The detail is under a single tab in Appendix B (tab lg,rg), with the fortis forms highlighted in red, and the <0> forms in purple.

⁹³ The <i> here is treated as an epenthetic spelling, allowing the obstruent to still count as a spelling of /rg/.

⁹⁴ The [r] here may have moved within the syllable, a common process with liquids, and reflected in the evolution of German *Ross* versus English *horse*. However, for the counts, this <ruch> is treated as a spelling of /urg/.

4.3.3.3) /g/ after nasal sonority

Notker provides 24 morphemes of syllable final /g/ after nasals.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/g <u>ang</u> /	<i>g<u>án</u>g</i>	'walk'
/v <u>ang</u> /	<i>u<u>á</u>ng</i>	'catch'
/- <u>ing</u> /	<i>-<u>ín</u>g</i>	suffix 'pertains to'
/br <u>ing</u> /	<i>br<u>ín</u>g</i>	'bring'
/ž <u>ing</u> /	<i>s<u>ín</u>g</i>	'sing'
/d <u>ing</u> /	<i>d<u>ín</u>g</i>	'thing'
/dw <u>ing</u> /	<i>duu<u>ín</u>g</i>	'coerce'
/l <u>ang</u> /	<i>l<u>án</u>g</i>	'long'
/r <u>ing</u> /	<i>r<u>ín</u>g</i>	'ring'
/dr <u>ing</u> /	<i>dr<u>ín</u>g</i>	'press'
/hon <u>ing</u> /	<i>hón<u>án</u>g</i>	'honey'
/j <u>ung</u> /	<i>i<u>ún</u>g</i>	'young'
/- <u>ling</u> /	<i>-<u>lín</u>g</i>	suffix 'pertains to'
/xl <u>ang</u> /	<i>chl<u>án</u>g</i>	'sound'
/l <u>ing</u> /	<i>l<u>ín</u>g</i>	'succeed'
/žpr <u>ing</u> /	<i>spr<u>ín</u>g</i>	'jump'
/- <u>ung</u> /	<i>-<u>un</u>g</i>	suffix 'pertains to'
/žl <u>ing</u> /	<i>sl<u>ín</u>g</i>	'perish'
/h <u>ang</u> /	<i>h<u>án</u>g</i>	'hang'
/bl <u>ang</u> /	<i>bl<u>án</u>g</i>	'white'
/m <u>ang</u> /	<i>m<u>án</u>g</i>	'many'
/žtr <u>ang</u> /	<i>str<u>án</u>g</i>	'strong'
/tsw <u>ing</u> /	<i>zu<u>ín</u>g</i>	'force'
/žt <u>ung</u> /	<i>st<u>ún</u>g</i>	'torment'

Across these 24 morphemes, Notker's Old Alemannic has /g/ syllable finally 640 times, with 79 of those marked fortis, and none marked with <θ>. Some examples are below, others and the rest of the data would be in Appendix B (tab Ng), where the fortis spellings are marked in red.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<ánafánc>	nom sg	II, 221, 15
<ánafánch>	acc sg	II, 108, 20
<dínch>	nom sg	II, 67, 10, 11; 237, 7; 239, 10; 290, 2; 335, 7
<dínc>	nom pl	II, 350, 5
<dínch>	nom pl	II, 11, 13
<dínc>	acc pl	II, 289, 9
<dínch>	acc pl	II, 23, 4; 34, 29; 38, 14; 270, 22; 283, 21; 286, 15; 287, 9; 333, 22; 334, 2; 335, 19; 339, 2
<iúnclichero>	gen sg fem	I, 695, 19
<iúnchlichero>	dat sg fem	I, 9, 9
<lánc>	uninflected	I, 852, 4
<erstráncta>	3rd sg past	I, 298, 26
<sánc>	acc sg	II, 408, 19
<sánch>	acc sg	II, 3299, 3
<stúncta>	3rd sg past	II, 104, 1

That gives a 12% fortition rate, which is lower than we might expect, after seeing a 40% rate in the labials. However, that 12% is still higher than the 9% rate for /g/ after liquids.

4.3.3.4) Additional on /g/

Perhaps it would be safest to quit here. We have worked through the stops, and our grid shows this.

Fortition	Vowels	Liquids	Nasals
/b/ -> [p]	2%	4-17%	40%
/d/ -> [t]	2-4%	12%	Spelling Rule
/g/ -> [k]	Spelling Rule {5%}	---- {9%}	---- {12%}

There is a good pattern here. In all three rows, syllable final fortition is inhibited less often after lesser degrees of preceding sonority. In addition, that pattern was pulled from lots of data (several thousand forms), makes phonological sense, and mirrors the

pattern syllable initially in the Anlautgesetz. Again, it might be safest just to stop.

Yet the author believes that the data for velars requires further analysis for it to be interpreted responsibly. The effort likely requires its own paper, as there may be several processes going on. What follows then will just be an introduction to the issues.

4.3.3.4.1) The effect of the spelling rule

Remember Page's grid, where he notes that Germanic */d/ (Alemannic /t/) is always written as <t> in /brejt/ [brájt] *bréit* 'wide, uninflected'. It was never written as **bréid*. That gave us zero free variation in our control group, so we were able to ignore the concept in our calculations of fortition being marked.

For the velar stops however, we also have [k] from /kx/ getting written via spelling rule as <g>.

/tag/ 'day'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/tag+ɪn/	[dáɡ+ɪn]	<dáɡen>	dat pl I, 50, 7
/tag/	[táɡ]	<táɡ>	nom sg I, 45, 22

/bokx/ 'billy goat'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/bokx+ɪn/	[bók.xən]	<bóccchen>	gen sg I, 708, 2
/bokx/	[pók]	<póg>	nom sg I, 291, 32

We have not calculated the percentage that this [k] from /k/ is written with a fortis graph. We need that percentage, in order to calculate out the effect of the spelling rule, out from the percentages we arrive at for /g/ getting written fortis.

This might get clearer with a walkthrough. Take, for example, two inflections for Notker's word for 'thought', one where the velar stop is word medial and one where word final.

/dan(k)x/ 'thought'	Spoken	Spelled	Inflection
/gɪ+dān(k)xɪ/	[gɪ.dānk.xɪ]	<gedánche>	dat sg II, 441, 16
/gɪ+dān(k)x/	[gɪ.dānk]	<gedáng>	nom sg I, 180, 12

The <g> in <gedáng> is clearly a [k] from /k/, 100% of the time. Moreover, when we list out all its examples, we see that its [k] from /k/ is marked <g> 46% of the time.

[k] from /k/ written <g>, conforming to the spelling rule	Count	Citation
<gedáng>	4	nom sg I, 180, 12 II, 202, 17; 520, 27; 529, 20
<gedáng>	2	acc sg I, 321, 18 II, 154, 15
<kedáng>	1	acc sg II, 134, 5
Percent written <g>:	7/13 54%	

[k] from /k/ written fortis, breaking with the spelling rule	Count	Citation
<gedánch>	2	nom sg II, 305, 20; 524, 24
<kedánch>	2	nom sg II, 354, 27; 389, 1
<gedánc>	1	nom sg II, 536, 9
<gedángh>	1	acc sg II, 134, 6
Percent written fortis:	6/13 46%	

For this one form, the marking of fortition breaks through the spelling rule 46% of the time. For sake of argument, assume this 46% is the percentage we end up with after counting all syllable final [k] from /k/ marked fortis after nasals (again, a project for another paper).

Such a calculation allows us to revisit the percentage of /g/ marked fortis after nasals, which was only 12%. However, if we assume, based on our analysis of [k] from /k/, that the spelling rule can be broken through only 46% of the time, then this 12% for /g/ marked as [k] is also only over 46% of the fortis spellings of /g/. The real fortition rate, once the effect of the spelling rule is factored out, would be:

$$\begin{array}{rcl} 46\% \text{ /k/ marked fortis} & & 12\% \text{ /g/ marked fortis} \\ \text{-----} & = & \text{-----} \\ 100\% \text{ fortis [k] from /k/} & & x\% \text{ fortis [k] from /g/} \end{array}$$

Cross-multiplying gives:

$$46x = 1200$$

To solve for x, we divide both sides by 46 to get:

$$x = 26\% \text{ fortis [k] from /g/}$$

That 26% fortition rate is nearer the 40% that we saw for syllable final /b/ after nasals.

4.3.3.4.2) Weakening in back consonants

Velar consonants tend to weaken.⁹⁵ The stops /g,k/ can weaken to the fricatives [ɣ,x], the fricatives [ɣ,x] to [j,h], and that final continuant then drop to zero.

You can see this reduction in modern languages. Compare Standard German *Tag* [tak] with how a Berliner might say the word [tax] versus their English gloss and cognate 'day'. Similarly, think about how Viennese German ends *heilig* with [ɪk], versus [ɪç] in the standard language, versus their English gloss and cognate 'holy'.

Is there evidence of this weakening in Notker?⁹⁶ To investigate, flip back to sections 4.3.3.2 and 4.3.3.3, where we listed syllable final fortis markings of /g/ after liquids and then nasals. For this discussion on weakening, include the two examples with <θ>. What jumps out is that after liquids, only one is written without an <h>.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<púr <u>cl</u> iche>	nom pl fem	I, 100, 21

That would be just 5%. The rest of the spellings, a few of which are pasted below, all mark fortition with an h-graph.

⁹⁵ Note how this discussion breaks with SPN01 pp. 42-43, which posited a guideline on not restricting a phonological rule's input by place unless conditioned by place. Even in SPN01 however, the author wrote that "it is doubtful that this function can stand unamended". Perhaps a revision integrating naturalness would help, as it is indeed natural for back consonants to spirantize and weaken.

⁹⁶ There certainly is between vowels. A pattern with *sláhen* and *slân* 'slay' is discussed in multiple articles. But here we are looking at the process syllable finally.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<búrch>	nom sg	II, 102, 7; 130, 13
<púrch>	nom sg	II, 224, 26
<búrch>	gen sg	II, 318, 12; 324, 16
<búrch>	dat sg	II, 473, 12 (2)
<búrgh>	dat sg	II, 482, 10
<púrchlíute>	nom pl	I, 660, 24

The letter <h>, whether in the graph <h>, <ch> or <cch>, normally marks continuancy in Notker's Alemannic (laryngeal, fricative, affricate), and either an [h] or maybe [θ] in his Ecclesiastical Latin. Graphs without an h, like <g,c,k,q> mostly mark a hard stop, in both Notker's Ecclesiastical Latin and his Old Alemannic.

Now glance through the list for /g/ after nasals. Of the 79 forms, the majority are still marked with an <h>. However 16 have the process marked with a hard stop graph <c,q,k>, so 20%. In addition, none of the forms after nasals is marked with zero.⁹⁷

That would make sense, if we are looking at these phonological rules in Notker:

⁹⁷ The author is not arguing that all spellings with <h> mark spirantization, just that there is a pattern of less of those and zero when we assume a stop from epenthesis. The graph <ch> may have been the most chosen graph to mark fortition, whether of /g/ to [k] or also spirantized to [x]. Nevertheless, we can draw on the math in section 4.3.3.4.1 to tease out that pattern, and arrive at the percentage of spirantization plus fortition vs just fortition or just spirantization.

	/Vg/		/Rg/		/Ng/	
Phonemic	/tag/ 'day'		/burg/ 'town'		/žang/ 'song'	
Nasal Assimilation					[žang]	[žan <u>ŋ</u>]
Fortition		[tá <u>k</u>]		[búr <u>k</u>]		[žan <u>k</u>]
Velar Weakening		[tá <u>x</u>]		[búr <u>x</u>]		[žan <u>x</u>]
Epenthesis						[žan <u>kx</u>]
Velar Deletion						[žan <u>k</u>]
Spelling Rules	<tá <u>g</u> >	<tá <u>ch</u> >	<búr <u>g</u> >	<búr <u>ch</u> >	<sá <u>g</u> >	<sá <u>ŋ</u> >

Here we have the /g/ syllable finally, after our three sonorant environments - after vowels, after liquids, and after nasals. For each environment, there are two scenarios listed. The one to the left is the standard, while the one to the right, which is italicized, shows the result if both Velar Weakening and Fortition took place. Note that, for the standard columns, there is no difference in how the /g/ is realized. They are all written <g>.

On the right, italicized column however, you see the merger of /g/ with /x/, which is marked here in the softer spelling of <ch>. Nevertheless, that is only the case after vowels and liquids. After nasals, the hard <g> spelling is retained. That is because Epenthesis and Velar Deletion work together to reverse out the effect of Fortition and Velar Weakening.

Such a future analysis would have to count all syllable final [k] from /kx/, to factor out the strength of the spelling rule. Then there is the guideline from SPN01, that scribes only mark phoneme mergers. A simple weakening of /g/ to [ɣ] would only be marked if it underwent an additional process, to merge with either /k/, /h/, /x/, or /θ/.

Between fortition, epenthesis, a spelling rule, velar weakening, and velar deletion, we are looking at quite a few processes to tease out from one another. Perhaps another paper may succeed in this. Alternatively, perhaps it will just flail around in the rabbit hole.

4.3.4) /v/ written fortis

SPN03 proposes a spelling rule in Notker, whereby word final /v/ is written <f> rather than <u>.⁹⁸ The rule is considered natural, because Latin (the source script for Notker's Old Alemannic) only uses <u> word finally to mark a vowel, never to mark a fricative.⁹⁹ Rather than restate those arguments, we can just list out the data.

4.3.4.1) /v/ after vocalic sonority

Notker provides only two or three morphemes where /v/ can occur syllable finally after vowels. The spellings word finally (w.f.) are in the first line of the cell, those word medially (w.m.) are in the second.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/br <u>ie</u> v/	w.f. <br <u>ie</u> f>, *<br <u>ie</u> u> w.m. <br <u>ie</u> e>	'letter'
/h <u>o</u> v/	w.f. <h <u>o</u> f>, *<h <u>o</u> u> w.m. <h <u>o</u> e>	'court'
*/t <u>se</u> l <u>(i)</u> v/	w.f. <zu <u>é</u> l <u>i</u> f>, *<zu <u>é</u> l <u>i</u> u> w.m. <zu <u>é</u> l <u>i</u> e>	'twelve'

⁹⁸ SPN03. pp. 42-43.

⁹⁹ Incidentally, the graph <v> is rarely used, although one sometimes sees it transcribed in the Firchow editions as a variant of <u> when marking an Old Alemannic [w] sequence, <uvinter> 'winter nom sg' I, 292, 2 (Nb22407 in Firchow). Sehrt and Firchow also frequently transcribe a <v> for the [u] after a [w] <ántuuvrta> 'answer, 1st sg past' I, 314, 15 (Nb23917 in Firchow). Regardless, <v> it is not a separate grapheme from <u> in Notker's Ecclesiastical Latin or his Old Alemannic. It is just an allograph of <u>.

In addition, the morpheme for 'twelve' should probably be discarded. First, should it be included in the list after vowels or after liquids? A form like *zuéLf* argues for the latter, although *zuéLif* predominates. More importantly, there are no examples of a /v/ being marked <u> here word medially - no *zuéliue*, only *zuéLife*. Perhaps we are no longer looking at an Old Alemannic /v/ from Germanic */f/ here, but a fricative that has been reanalyzed as /f/.¹⁰⁰

Another disappointment is the morpheme /hev/, cognate with English 'heave' and 'heavy', and of course German 'heben'. In the verb, we have Werner's Law, which means the 1st and 3rd singular past end in /b/, so *huob*. The 2nd singular imperative ends with vowel, *heue*, while derivatives off the verb, like *héui* 'weight' and *héuig* 'weighty', keep the /v/ syllable initial and word medial.

Nevertheless, of the two morphemes that do end in /v/ after vowels, there are zero forms that have the /v/ written <u> word finally (or even word medially, before an inflection ending). All nine forms are written with <f>. The data are in Appendix B (tab Vv).

Form	Inflection	Citation
<kebr <u>ief</u> te>	past part	I, 767, 24
<missebr <u>ief</u> ta>	3rd sg past	I, 68, 20
<br <u>ief</u> p <u>uo</u> che>	dat sg	II, 271, 18
<br <u>ief</u> p <u>uo</u> chen>	dat pl	I, 762, 17
<h <u>ó</u> f>	nom sg	I, 736, 26 II, 404, 9, 10; 566, 18
<h <u>ó</u> f>	acc sg	I, 771, 7

¹⁰⁰ The word for 'eleven' is even less promising. Notker only has it as an ordinal, so with the /v/ or /f/ always followed by a dental stop, and always written <f>. Examples would be <éinluften> 'eleventh, acc sg masc wk' II, 546, 19 and <éinliftûn> 'eleventh, dat sg fem wk' I, 737, 28.

Does this point to a 100% fortition rate for labial fricatives after vowels? That seems unlikely, as we had less than single percentage fortition in this environment for /b/, /d/, and /g/. However, an absolute pattern, like one written 100% of the time, does make sense for a spelling rule.¹⁰¹

4.3.4.2) /v/ after liquid sonority

Similar to after vowels, we see very few examples of /v/ after liquids. There may only be the word for 'wolf' /wolv/ and its appellative /-olv/, in *náhtolf*, *ríchoľf*, and *uuíľľolf* 'god of night', 'rich man', and 'god of will'. Unfortunately, those three forms with the appellative do not provide an inflected form, where we could see if the word final <f> in *-olf* could be written <u> word medially, like *náhtolues*.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/wolv/	w.f. <uuóľ <u>f</u> >, *<uuóľ <u>u</u> > w.m. <uuóľ <u>ua</u> >	'wolf'
/-olv/	w.f. <náhtol <u>f</u> >, *<náhtol <u>u</u> > w.m. Not Found	'wolf'

There does not seem to be an example after /r/. Nevertheless, of the two morphemes that do end in /v/ after liquids, there are zero forms that have the /v/ written <u> word finally. All five forms are written with <f>. The data are in Appendix B (tab Nv,lv,rv).

Form	Inflection	Citation
<náhtol <u>f</u> >	nom sg	I, 735, 21; 738, 14
<ríchoľ <u>f</u> >	nom sg	II, 186, 22
<uuíľľol <u>f</u> >	nom sg	I, 737, 25
<uuóľ <u>f</u> >	nom sg	II, 345, 2

Does this point to a 100% fortition rate for labial fricatives after liquids? As with the situation after vowels, this seems unlikely, as

¹⁰¹ As mentioned earlier, SPN03 addresses this question in depth.

we are averaging only about a 12% fortition in this environment for /b,d,g/. However, an absolute pattern, like one written 100% of the time, does make sense for a spelling rule.¹⁰²

4.3.4.3) /v/ after nasal sonority

As detailed in the introduction to section 4, the situation after nasals is likely not interpretable. There are just too few data and too many potential processes.

Nevertheless, we can still list the forms. There may only be two, the words for 'five' and 'soft'. The data are in Appendix B (tab Nv,lv,rv).

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/vi <u>NV</u> /	w.f. <u <u>ín</u> f>, *<u <u>ínu</u> > w.m. <u <u>ínu</u> iu>	'five'
/ž <u>an</u> V <u>T</u> +j/	w.f. Not Found w.m. <un <u>sén</u> fte>, <sá <u>m</u> f <u>t</u> o>	'soft'

By now we are expecting a spelling rule, to confirm that only <f> is written word finally for the fricative after nasals, as was the case after vowels and liquids. Notker does not disappoint us.¹⁰³

Form	Inflection	Citation
<f <u>ín</u> f>	uninflected	I, 66, 26; 162, 14; 197, 28(2); 339, 25; 699, 4; 729, 20; 750, 13; 751, 10
<u <u>ín</u> f>	uninflected	I, 489, 4
<f <u>ún</u> f>	uninflected	II, 424, 7; 429, 11(2); 482, 17

¹⁰² Again, see SPN03.

¹⁰³ The pattern <nft> in words like *chúnftig*, *nôtnúnftâra*, *úngezúnfto* is interesting, and at first glance could be used as a counter-example to nasal assimilation. However, the forms may be better understood if we include their historical dental preterite, so *chúnftig* marks [xúnr.fti:g] from /xun+r+Fr+i:g/. When there is not a syllable boundary to break up the consonant string, the first dental stop seems to drop out, and the string reduce to [mpft], reflected in the spelling <mft> in *úngezúmft*. The data is in Appendix B (tab Nv,lv,rv), at the lower left column, where forms with /m(p)f/ [mpf] are also listed for comparison. A side effect of this analysis is that it establishes [ft] as a syllable onset in Notker (section 4.2.5).

4.3.5) /ž/ written fortis

SPN02 details how Notker's /ž/ and /s/ differ in more than just fortition, and that scribes only mark the mergers of phonemes, not phonological processes. Notker would then not mark the fortition of /ž/, as it would only change to [š], and so not merge with /s/.

This holds nearly 100% of the time. For example, as already cited in section 4.3, Notker writes hundreds of examples of the words for 'until' and 'pronoun 1st person dat pl', glossed and cognate with English 'us'. Nevertheless, the count of /UNŽ/ [únž] uns 'us' being written as fortis unz is zero. Moreover, that zero is equal to the count of the reverse, where /UNS/ [únts] únz 'until' is written zero times as lenis úns.

The data are in Appendix B (tabs Vž and Nž,lž,rž).

4.3.6) /h/ written fortis

We have multiple issues with our final investigation, /h/ written fortis syllable finally:

- 1) As with the dental fricatives, the phonemes /h/ and /x/ differ in more than just fortition.¹⁰⁴ A simple fortition would not be marked, as scribes mark the merger of phonemes, not phonological processes.
- 2) As with the velar stops, a spelling rule obscures any processes, as [x] and [h] are both written <h> word finally.¹⁰⁵

¹⁰⁴ See SPN02 for /h/ syllable initially, and SPN03 for the phoneme syllable finally.

¹⁰⁵ SPN01. pp. 119 - 124, plus all of SPN03.

- 3) The weakening sketched out with /g/ and /k/ is likely taking place with /h/ and /x/.
- 4) There is a constraint on the laryngeal /h/ in Notker. When inflections place /h/ next to a consonant (without a syllable boundary in between), the laryngeal is replaced with either [x] or [∅].

4.3.6.1) /h/ after vocalic sonority

There is very little marking of a collapse of /h/ to [x] syllable finally after vowels, and written perhaps as <ch>. Instead, /na:h/ nâh 'after', cognate with English 'nigh', occurs hundreds of times, but never as *nâch. It is the same with /doh/ dôh glossed and cognate with English 'though', which occurs hundreds of times, but only once as <dôch> I, 683, 20 (also once without any consonant, <dô> II, 189, 21). There are again hundreds of /noh/ nôh 'furthermore', cognate with English 'enough', but only one <nôch> II, 18, 15.

Of course, there is the spelling rule, so any marking of fortition here would need to first calculate that, the percentage of [x] from /x/ written as <ch>. An example would be <brâch> 'break, 3rd sg past' II, 219, 11, where the spelling rule would normally generate <brâh> I, 810, 17. Similar would also be <sprâch> 'speak, 3rd sg past' I, 615, 19, where the spelling rule would normally generate <sprâh> I, 35, 13.

4.3.6.2) /h/ after liquid sonority

There are maybe only two morphemes here.

Morpheme	Spelling	Gloss
/velh/	w.f. <beuá <u>lh</u> >, <pefá <u>lch</u> >, <befá <u>l</u> > w.m. <beué <u>leh</u> endo>	'entrust'
/vurh/	w.f. Not Found w.m. <fú <u>rehe</u> >	'furrow'

Unfortunately, the word for 'furrow' only occurs when inflected. Syllable finally then, we have only the /h/ after /l/ to investigate. There are only four forms, but all quite interesting, as syllable final /h/ is realized either as [∅] or as [x], somewhat arbitrarily. When [∅], there is of course no letter. When [x], the spelling mostly follows the rule and is written <h>, but one spelling of <ch> breaks through.

Form	Inflection	Citation
<beuá <u>l</u> h>	3rd sg past	I, 74, 30 II, 313, 1; 447, 25
<peuá <u>l</u> h>	3rd sg past	I, 29, 22
<pefá <u>l</u> ch>	3rd sg past	II, 567, 21
<befá <u>l</u> >	3rd sg past	II, 480, 15

When syllable initial, the variation is between [∅] and [h], as in:

Form	Inflection	Citation
<beuó <u>l</u> ehen>	past part	II, 413, 14
<peuó <u>l</u> en>	past part	I, 76, 1

The middle <e> in the first form looks to be an epenthetic spelling (to mark [h], as opposed to [x]), but it could also be interpreted phonologically as an epenthetic schwa.

4.3.6.3) /h/ after nasal sonority

Notker does not have morphemes where /h/ follows a nasal. This is likely because of a sound change in Germanic, where nasals deleted between a vowel and Germanic */h/. We see this where a Germanic */h/ varied with a Germanic */g/ that did not trigger deletion of the nasal. Examples are the English verb pair *bring/brought* and Notker's Old Alemannic *uîeng/uáhen* 'catch'.

5) Notker's Verhärtung

Again, the grid for the Auslautverhärtung in Notker would be:

Fortition	Vowels	Liquids	Nasals
/b/ -> [p]	2%	4-17%	40%
/d/ -> [t]	2-4%	12%	Spelling Rule
/g/ -> [k]	Spelling Rule {5%}	---- {9%}	---- {12%}
/v/ -> [f]	Spelling Rule	----	----
/ž/ -> [s]	Phonemes not merged	----	----
/h/ -> [x]	Spelling Rule and Phonemes not merged	----	----

It appears that syllable final fortition in Notker is governed by the same gradation in sonority that governs the process syllable initially. That means that Notker's fortition rule need no longer be subsetted into three parts, based on the obstruent's position in a syllable, as was done in SPN01.¹⁰⁶

Since this new rule includes two elements in gradation, it might be cleaner to express it in just prose, rather than in binary feature notation. Moreover, we need a simpler title, as the rule no longer specifies "Anlaut" or "Auslaut".

Notker's Verhärtung

Obstruents in Notker's Old Alemannic become fortis, unless that fortition is inhibited by a preceding sonorant. The ability of the preceding sonorant to inhibit fortition is gradated by two elements - the sonorant's degree of sonority and the sonorant's degree of distance from the following obstruent.

¹⁰⁶ SPN01. pp. 72-79.